

Proceedings of the third openLCA conference

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Preface

Various software solutions are employed for conducting Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs). GreenDelta has been at the forefront of this field since 2006, developing the open-source software openLCA, which is highly suitable for LCA studies. Over the years, openLCA has gained global recognition as the most extensively used LCA software. It provides the broadest selection of databases for LCA software, boasting over 300,000 unique datasets.

In recent years, openLCA has seen significant advancements, not only as a standalone tool but also as a solution integrated with other sustainability tools and add-ons. Complementary tools, such as the LCA Collaboration Server, have facilitated cooperation among LCA practitioners and have also enabled the creation and publication of additional databases. Furthermore, due to its low entry barrier and the availability of resources, openLCA has been widely adopted for LCA studies, projects, and research worldwide.

After the sold-out success of the first conference and second, bigger, openLCA conference in 2025, GreenDelta now gears up for the third edition of the openLCA conference. This document holds the proceedings of the third openLCA conference, to be held in Berlin, Germany, from the 22nd to 23rd of April, 2026. openLCA.conf serves as a networking and exchange platform for openLCA users and enthusiasts. The conference emphasizes the participants' engagement with the software and sheds light on the latest advancements. The following topics will be discussed at the conference:

- *Advancing EPDs*
- *Agriculture & bioeconomy*
- *Buildings: LCAs and climate mitigation strategies*
- *End-of-Life strategies*
- *Energy systems*
- *Innovation in LCA data creation, LCI databases, Validating LCA datasets*
- *openLCA tools and integration*
- *Social LCA case studies*
- *Sustainability assessment of plastics*
- *System dynamics and LCSA*
- *Regulations and sustainability frameworks*

All abstracts presented in this document were peer reviewed by experienced LCA professionals.

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Oral

Advancing EPDs: Data Quality, Automation, and Integration

Towards Automated EPD Generation: A Python Framework for Integrated Upstream Modelling in openLCA

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Abstract:

The growing adoption of Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) across manufacturing sectors highlights the need for faster, consistent, and standardised workflows. While openLCA provides robust capabilities for life cycle modelling, the upstream phases of EPD development—such as extracting material information from Bills of Materials (BOMs), identifying supplier locations, assigning transport routes and distances, and converting raw industrial data into structured process datasets—remain largely manual. These early steps often represent a bottleneck, introducing variability, limiting reproducibility, and increasing the workload for LCA practitioners.

This work presents a Python-based framework designed to automate these phases and generate process datasets that can be directly integrated into openLCA. The tool automatically parses BOM files that follow a standardised template, aggregates materials by country of origin, and models supply-chain transport flows through a flexible and extensible architecture. Transport activities are modelled through a hybrid approach that combines automated distance calculation with the option to manually refine or supplement routes. This dual automatic–manual mechanism allows scalability while ensuring that practitioners retain the ability to incorporate specific knowledge, maintaining efficiency and high data quality.

Based on the processed material and transport information, the framework generates openLCA-ready intermediate structures and files (Excel/JSON) that explicitly represent processes, flows, exchanges, and mapping specifications. These intermediate datasets are both machine-readable, allowing seamless import into openLCA, and human-readable, providing a transparent record of assumptions, calculations, and data sources. Their clarity and traceability make them suitable not only for automated database import but also for inclusion in EPD documentation and LCA reports.

By transforming fragmented industrial information into structured, openLCA-compatible datasets with minimal user intervention, the framework reduces modelling time, improves reproducibility, and facilitates scalable EPD workflows in industrial contexts. The work

demonstrates how automating pre-processing, transport modelling, and intermediate dataset creation can significantly streamline the integration of EPD generation within openLCA-based LCA infrastructures.

Scaling EPDs: From Verified Type III to Enterprise Automation — A Joint Project by Fraunhofer IEM and WAGO

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Abstract:

In collaboration with Fraunhofer IEM, WAGO presents the journey from a first standalone life cycle assessment (LCA) for a splicing connector to a verified EPD Type III, and further towards an automated, scalable EPD tool integrated into enterprise IT systems. The verified EPD, the parameterized model, and key findings are already available; full integration is planned for 2026. This progressive approach combines methodology, high-quality data and IT architecture to enable a scalable and auditable system — reflecting the strategic transition in EPD programmes from individual declaration verification to the validation of calculation tools and underlying processes, enabling repeatable and scalable EPD generation.

The first part highlights the implementation of the initial EPD Type III and the challenges encountered even with a seemingly simple product: non-existing or inconsistency PCR, change from EPD to PEP and back to EPD, a transition from single-EPD thinking to system scaling, data gaps in production processes, and insufficient supplier documentation for sustainable materials. We demonstrate how model parameterization, adaptive data filtering and accurate PLM representation provide the technical foundation for automation — enabling consistent BOM mapping, variant handling, and robust material assignments. Our experience with the EN 15804 library is shared, including how modelling decisions were documented and made audit-ready.

The second part focuses on embedding LCA as a core component of product development. A resilient data structure, defined trigger points and clear governance ensure that product changes automatically initiate recalculations, while versioning and traceability safeguard quality. OpenLCA serves as the computational backbone, connected through flexible interfaces. Automated recalculation is orchestrated via a Python pipeline that enables synchronous workflows and is designed to incorporate AI-supported elements in the future (e.g., automated data matching suggestions, plausibility checks). Product carbon footprint (PCF) calculations and full LCAs then provide a foundation to link sustainability data directly to engineering and sourcing decisions — depending on customer expectations and verification levels.

Our three-stage path to automation: Stage 1 automatically determines the Product Carbon Footprint within development, reducing manual effort and providing reliable decision support. Stage 2 performs a full life cycle assessment across all phases—from raw material extraction to manufacturing, use, and end-of-life—for a holistic environmental evaluation. Stage 3 verifies the results and publishes Environmental Product Declarations to ensure external transparency, comparability, and compliance.

The outcome is a transferable roadmap—from the verified single PEP to IT-enabled, automated EPD generation—fast, scalable, and credible.

The GCCA EPD tool: An industry-wide solution for cement and concrete products based on openLCA

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Abstract:

The Global Cement and Concrete Association (GCCA) Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) Tool is a sector-specific solution designed exclusively to support the generation of standardized and compliant Environmental Product Declarations for cementitious materials. As the demand for credible, comparable, and transparent environmental reporting increases across the construction value chain, ensuring methodological integrity and ease of maintenance in EPD tools has become essential.

To address this, the GCCA EPD Tool has been enhanced with an openLCA-based backend, enabling a more flexible, modular, and future-proof calculation framework. The integration with openLCA significantly improves the capacity to update and maintain the tool, especially in relation to background LCA datasets, evolving Product Category Rules (PCRs), and future methodological changes aligned with EN 15804 and ISO 14040/44. The new backend also simplifies model management, increases transparency of underlying assumptions, and allows faster deployment of updates globally—ensuring the tool remains synchronized with the latest standards and datasets relevant to cement and concrete EPDs.

This presentation will outline the technical architecture of the enhanced tool, demonstrate how openLCA improves usability and adaptability for EPD generation, and highlight the resulting benefits for data governance and reporting consistency. Looking ahead, the tool will be further expanded with a connection to the soda4LCA API to support the integration of background dataset updates and validation workflows. In parallel, development is underway to transform the platform into a future fully pre-verified EPD system, enabling automated verification and reducing economic and administrative burdens for producers. With these advancements, the GCCA EPD Tool is evolving into a globally aligned, scalable, and verification-ready digital infrastructure supporting the cement and concrete sector's transition toward transparent and credible environmental reporting.

Towards Digitalization of EPDs: Challenges and Opportunities – A Program Operator’s Perspective

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Abstract:

The growing use of Environmental product declarations (EPD) in the market has resulted in growing number of digital tools designed to support their creation. These tools differ widely in their structure, level of automation, data handling, scope, and features. From a program operator’s standpoint, this diversity presents both opportunities and complexities. Digital solutions can streamline EPD workflows by automating calculations, reducing manual data entry, and standardizing modelling steps. However, they also introduce challenges related to inconsistency and lack of transparency.

At EPD International AB, we see a growing need for clearer guidance and increased digitalization across the market. To support more robust digital practices, we have introduced a fully digital EPD format known as the Compiler. The Compiler offers a structured web-based environment where all required EPD information is captured in a defined, machine-readable form. It includes built-in validation functions that monitor completeness, consistency, and alignment with rule requirements. These validation features are regularly reviewed and improved to better match PCR specifications and ensure higher data quality. The Compiler also maintains version control for every submission, allowing verifiers to track changes across different iterations of an EPD. This ensures full transparency of updates and strengthens the integrity of the verification process. The Compiler also features an upstream RESTful API that enables seamless integration with LCA tools such as openLCA. This allows direct transfer of structured data into the Compiler, reducing manual effort and minimizing transcription errors. It also avoids information loss associated with document-based formats, increasing interoperability across digital systems. Looking ahead, ongoing efforts focus on strengthening digital validation, harmonizing guidance, and supporting tool developers through clearer expectations. A growing challenge is the expansion and revision of regulations and different standards which introduce new requirements and methodological updates. These updates often arrive with shortened implementation timelines, putting pressure on program operators to rapidly adjust systems and guidance, and giving tool owners even less time to respond. Strategically, the future consistency, transparency, and credibility of digital EPD generation will

be defined by how effectively digital tools can keep pace with evolving rules and integrate them both rapidly and reliably.

Agriculture & Bioeconomy

Holistic and Integrated Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment of Community Supported Agriculture: A Case Study of School Catering in Leipzig, Germany

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Abstract:

Global food supply and intensive agriculture significantly impact social, economic, and ecological sustainability. Community Supported Agriculture (CSA) strives to transform regional food networks by connecting producers and consumers. Although intrinsically more sustainable due to agroecological farming, short supply chains, and regional cooperation, no assessment has yet quantified the sustainability benefits of CSA. No Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) has been conducted in Germany, and only a few studies have been carried out in Europe to identify the impacts and improvement potentials of CSA. A Holistic and Integrated Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (HILCSA) was applied to a CSA in Leipzig, Germany, offering a novel integrative approach to analyze CSA benefits and impacts compared to a conventional reference in all three sustainability dimensions. Seven different fruits and vegetables produced by the CSA and distributed to schools in Leipzig were assessed. Based on 82 indicators, the results showed that CSA has 63% fewer sustainability risks compared to the conventional German food market. All substitution factors of impacts aggregated to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were below 1.0, indicating a positive contribution by the CSA. Additionally, replacing conventional supply with supply from the CSA to 200 pupils can avoid 1 ton of CO₂ equivalents over one school year. Resource efficiency emerged as a key area for improvement, as the CSA had significantly lower yields than conventional production. However, it had similar water, land, and energy uses per hectare. At the same time, the highest upstream impacts were caused by Spent Mushroom Substrate (SMS) applied as organic fertilizer. The findings highlight the potential of CSA to drive regional socio-ecological transformation while suggesting improvements in resource efficiency.

The Missing Impact: A Case Study Investigation into Assessing Biodiversity Impacts in LCA through Antarctic Krill Harvesting and Brazilian Soya Production

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Abstract:

The triple planetary crisis of climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution threatens our society, the environment and the economy. These challenges interconnect and reinforce each other, amplifying their combined impacts. Existing Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) studies mainly quantify greenhouse gas emissions, energy demand, and chemical pollution from processing operations but typically overlook biodiversity loss, a major driver of a cascade of ecosystem alteration and downfall. For example, current trawling and harvesting activities are concentrated in locations overlapping with predator feeding grounds and nursery habitats, creating direct competition in ecosystems already stressed by climate change.

This presentation addresses the methodological gap in LCA biodiversity assessment by comparing frameworks applicable to two contrasting systems: Antarctic krill harvesting and Brazilian soya production. Both industries operate in biodiversity-rich regions where extraction creates measurable ecological consequences, but current LCA practice treats these impacts as externalities beyond system boundaries. Through systematic evaluation of current biodiversity assessment methods, this research examines whether holistic environmental assessment can capture both industrial efficiency and ecological opportunity cost. The analysis reveals fundamental tensions between standardised LCA approaches developed for terrestrial agriculture and the requirements for assessing wild-capture fisheries in vulnerable polar ecosystems, with implications for how environmental science quantifies the true cost of resource extraction.

From residue to resource: consequential LCA of hazelnut shell valorisation pathways

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Abstract:

With the growing focus on minimising waste and developing greener products, circular bioeconomy has received increased attention. Many agricultural residues offer valuable chemical and material properties, but they remain underutilised. Valorising agri-food residues minimises waste streams and introduces environmental cost-effective products to replace petrochemical and bio-based products from first generation feedstocks (Yaashikaa et al. 2022).

One such agri-food with underutilised residues is the hazelnut, where more than half of the mass is made up of discarded residues, among which the hazelnut shell makes up the largest share (approx. 45-55% of the total mass). These residues are rich in lignin, oil, polyphenols, and cellulose which can be extracted and used as applications in the rubber, pharmaceutical, and cosmetics industries (Ceylan et al 2023).

To evaluate whether these new utilisation pathways are environmentally viable, a consequential LCA approach is useful as it considers the displaced current application of the residue (e.g. the shell) (Dominguez et al. 2023; Bishop et al. 2025). As the hazelnut shell is the dependent co-product, it has a constrained supply. Hence, demanding it for rubber production will displace its current use (e.g. incineration, bioenergy etc.), which can imply substitution by a marginal supplier (e.g. natural gas for energy supply).

However, determining the current application for the residue is not straightforward. It requires knowledge of regional market conditions and technologies (Güldemund et al. 2025; Tonini et al. 2016), and then the model will likely be influenced by the available background datasets (Rebolledo-Leiva et al. 2023). For many agricultural products, few to no suitable datasets on production and waste treatment exist in databases like ecoinvent, which is most commonly used. This renders screening LCAs more difficult and uncertain, and for more intermediate or comprehensive LCA studies, sound and reliable LCA results depend on comprehensive access to primary, local data.

A hazelnut shell LCA study was performed using the openLCA collaboration server to better support team-working and the ecoinvent v3.11 consequential library. Based on the LCA case study, this project aims at investigating methodological and practical challenges for consequential LCA modelling of valorisation systems for agri-food residues. These challenges primarily concern developing justifiable assumptions for current residue application as well as appropriately addressing modelling uncertainties related to limitations of lab-scale data and insufficient datasets. Furthermore, efforts to properly manage collaboration networks are explored with the intent of supporting data practices and ultimately increase data quality and availability.

Perspectives of shifting from chemical to physical phytosanitary treatments: preliminary integrated assessments through LCA and multicriteria methods

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Abstract:

Many efforts have been made to reduce impacts, especially related to drift, of phytosanitary treatments. Two of the most interesting alternatives are based on physical treatments: UV-C radiation and ozone-based. The latter is an “intermediate solution”: physical means are used to produce ozone – when necessary and in real time – that then acts chemically against pathogens. For both, application cases are still very rare, often limited to experimental activities on prototypes. Commercial solutions are mainly focused on greenhouse cultivation or post-harvest activities, with applications on stationary equipment dedicated to sanitisation or sterilisation. However, it is possible to identify some advantages and challenges. The main advantages concern:

1. no persistent residues, from drift, in the environment;
2. role of sanitising support, reducing the number of agrochemical treatments;
3. more flexible supply chain of the production factors, with simplifications in storage management;
4. the need to operate with dedicated equipment;
5. requirement of standard protective solutions.

Both solutions also have weaknesses. In the case of ozone, two independent sprayers are required (one technologically modified to carry out ozonation processes and the other to manage conventional chemical treatments) and both the annual supply of ozone in cylinders and the activation times for preparing the ozone-water mixture before each treatment must be considered. In the case of UV-C, in addition to the acquisition of specialised machines (which are equipped with lamps that require careful management for use in extreme environments), the best results are obtained with night-time treatments and operating in a stop&go mode according to a prescriptive map.

Comparative open field trials have not yet been able to identify clear advantages of physical vs. chemical treatments. Nevertheless, for both, reductions of up to 50% of agrochemicals

consumption can be expected, as well as a possible reduction in the number of treatments carried out during the season. Preliminary LCA results show that the greatest improvements can be expected in impact categories related to toxicity and carbon footprint indicators (with reduction that can be preliminary estimated in the ranges 25-40% and 5-10%, respectively).

Because of the many aspects involved and the early stage of use of the technologies an integrated assessment that simultaneously takes into account economic, operational and socio-environmental criteria and different decision-makers' priorities is essential here. The analysis is completed by a multi-criteria multi-stakeholder assessment considering various scenarios that could be envisaged for a wine-growing farm in a mountainous area of Northern Italy.

Carbon Footprint of Soy-Based Products Under PEFCR

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Abstract:

This abstract presents the study of six product carbon footprints (PCF), according to the Product Environmental Footprint Category Rule (PEFCR) Feed for Food-Producing Animals: soy protein concentrate (SPC), lecithin and refined oil, produced either from a genetically modified (GMO) or non-GMO soybeans in Brazil by CJ Selecta. The non-GMO SPC is exported to Norway, where serves as a feed ingredient for salmon feed production, which required PEFCR compliance. The study contemplates soy cultivation and industrial processing in a cradle-to-gate system boundary.

For the cultivation stage, major farmers, representing 80% of GMO and non-GMO soy volume, were grouped into three levels based on management or technology applied to cropping systems, as established by PEFCR. Sample sizes were established for each group according to the Pareto Principle and PAS 2050-1:2012, and data collection conducted with selected growers. As soy is an annual crop, three year-crops were assessed to level out differences in crop yields related to fluctuations in growing conditions. Inventory was modeled using ICVCalc, a tool developed by the Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation (Embrapa) that integrates models from other protocols and specific edaphoclimatic and technical parameters for Brazilian agricultural regions.

For GMO farmers, land use change (LUC) emissions were calculated using the BRLUC (Brazilian Land Use Change) Method, also by Embrapa, which estimates direct LUC and emissions associated with Brazilian agricultural products, at a municipality level. For non-GMO farmers, LUC was estimated through primary farm-level data collection, using satellite images for a 20-year period.

For the industrial phase, primary data was collected in the time frame of one year. Product system modelling was performed in OpenLCA, using the ecoinvent database and economic allocation. Results, verified according to ISO 14067.

The study shows that agriculture operations are the main contributors to the footprints (i.e.: 81% for non-GMO SPC and 87% for GMO SPC), especially due to fuel consumption in agricultural machinery and LUC. A sensitivity analysis was conducted for non-GMO SPC to evaluate the difference between LUC data from MapBiomas (primary satellite data), BRLUC and ecoinvent. The analysis revealed substantial variation among results and uncertainty, as displayed in the following graphic, reinforcing the importance of primary data collection in LCA studies.

Buildings: LCAs and climate mitigation strategies

Accounting for Permanence: Rethinking Carbon Storage Methodologies for Bio-based Building Materials

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Abstract:

Bio-based construction materials are increasingly recognised for their potential to sequester carbon. Yet, the methodological frameworks governing life cycle assessment and environmental product declarations (EPDs) remain ill-equipped to quantify long-term or permanent carbon storage. This paper explores this gap through the experience of emerging manufacturers of bio-based and mineral-bonded materials, with a focus on GreenJams, an Indian startup that utilises agricultural residues such as paddy straw within mineral matrices to produce structural materials with verifiable carbon storage potential.

Monk Spaces conducted the life cycle assessment and published a third-party verified EPD for this product under PCR 2019:14. However, the EPD was later flagged because the PCR excludes the declaration of permanent carbon storage. This allowance existed in the previous version through the provision for alternate results. This change exposed a crucial methodological and policy disconnect: while static biogenic carbon models assume eventual release to the atmosphere, mineral-bonded bio-based materials can effectively lock carbon for centuries, achieving storage permanence comparable to geological sequestration.

The paper discusses how such cases challenge the existing boundaries of LCA standards, verification processes, and policy instruments designed around short-lived bio-based systems. It identifies three areas requiring methodological evolution: (1) integrating permanence and reversibility risk into the carbon accounting framework, (2) establishing verification mechanisms that accommodate empirical evidence from product-specific assessments, and (3) restoring flexibility in PCRs to permit transparent reporting of alternate or sensitivity results where justified.

By situating this discussion within the context of rapidly growing innovation ecosystems in emerging markets, the paper demonstrates how methodological rigidity can inadvertently penalise credible climate-positive materials. It argues for an approach to LCA and EPD development that combines rigour with adaptability—one that reflects the actual carbon behaviour of new material systems rather than constraining them within outdated

assumptions. Through this dialogue, the work contributes to the global effort to position buildings not merely as consumers of resources but as durable, verifiable carbon sinks capable of advancing climate mitigation goals.

KEYWORDS:

carbon storage, bio-based materials, permanence, LCA methodology, PCR 2019:14, EPD revision, embodied carbon, emerging markets

Dynamic climate change assessment: a method to accurately evaluate the effect of carbon storage in building materials

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Abstract:

Thanks to a dynamic approach, this study aims to question the -1/+1 hypothesis imposed by the EN 15804+A2 standard regarding biogenic carbon. Bio-based materials sequester carbon dioxide at the production stage. The distinction between materials derived from agricultural annual plants and those derived from forestry products must be made. However, moving from the tree scale to the landscape scale, the rotation period of trees is no longer important, and the CO₂ uptake of wood materials is modelled similarly to agricultural materials. Regarding end-of-life, bio-based materials might follow different waste disposal scenarios. Each scenario implies different greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, emission kinetics and long-term carbon storage. Hence, the authors recommend guidelines to determine dynamic GHGs inventories, whether the material is mulched, composted, incinerated, or landfilled.

A dynamic GHGs inventory is also needed for mineral materials, as they progressively sequester carbon through carbonation. Based on recent literature, we propose a way to properly account for carbonation of lime and cementitious materials.

Using dynamic climate change assessments (dCCA), structural, insulating, as well as other envelope materials are evaluated. By combining the dynamics of biogenic carbon uptake and release as well as carbonation, dCCA enable to assess climate impacts of product systems with more clarity, transparency and understanding.

We show that the -1/+1 approach imposed by the EN 15804+A2 norm clearly overestimates the climate impacts of bio-based materials. Consequently, we suggest other indicators than the global warming potential at a 100-year time horizon (GWP₁₀₀) to properly include the effect of carbon storage for bio-based products. The use of a corrected GWP₁₀₀ with time corrective factors, as well as cumulative radiative forcing ΔF and global mean temperature change ΔT metrics, is proposed.

However, as biogenic carbon sequestration compensates fossil emissions, the promotion of carbon storage by bio-based products might lead to a transfer of pollution: oversized bio-based products in buildings leading to over-harvesting. As a result, dynamic climate change indicators combined with a resource depletion indicator appear important to ensure sustainable biomass withdrawal rates. These recommendations aim to encourage a frugal design of buildings that might fit with climate neutrality at both short- and long-term perspectives.

Case Study on Developing National LCI Data for Korean Wood Products through LCA Analysis

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Abstract:

The growing demand for quantitative environmental information in policy making and product certification has increased the importance of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). A reliable Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) database is essential for accurate LCA, as results vary greatly depending on the quality and relevance of the underlying data. Ideally, LCI datasets should reflect real manufacturing conditions by process and product type, yet locally representative datasets remain limited.

In Korea, national carbon neutrality policies have encouraged the expansion of wood use, prompting efforts to improve LCI data for wood-based materials. The National Institute of Forest Science (NIFoS) has been building and updating national LCI datasets for legally defined intermediate wood products. As wooden buildings gain attention as an effective means of increasing wood utilization, recent reviews have highlighted significant data gaps for major engineered wood components used in modern timber construction.

To address this, the present study developed national LCI datasets for two key wood products widely applied in architecture—glued laminated timber (glulam) and cross-laminated timber (CLT)—for which no domestic datasets previously existed. The assessment followed a cradle-to-gate boundary, including resource extraction, material processing, and product manufacturing. Site-specific production data were collected to enhance accuracy and representativeness.

The resulting datasets are expected to improve the reliability of LCAs involving Korean wood products and support environmental evaluation and policy development related to wooden construction. However, the analysis still relies on several assumptions due to limited domestic data availability, and many background processes required the use of foreign databases. This underscores the need for further development of comprehensive, locally representative LCI datasets for wood-related manufacturing processes in Korea to strengthen future LCA applications.

Carbon storage in the Swiss buildings stock, methodological pathways and accounting approaches

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Abstract:

This contribution examines the potential carbon storage in the Swiss building stock. It illustrates accounting approaches and methodological pathways for the temporary storage in biogenic construction materials.

Analyses by the Swiss Federal Office of Energy outline the expected decarbonization pathway for buildings and identify carbon storage potentials (BFE, 2024). The identified potentials could offset the sector's remaining emissions in 2050. The Swiss framework for the building assessments defining target and limit values underscores the need to link the crediting of the storage to demonstrable reductions in operational and embodied emissions (SIA 390/1, 2025).

Mineral-based solutions for carbon storage, such as carbonation of recycled concrete granulate, are widely accepted as contribution to negative emissions. Certificates however have been sold to external actors. This practice challenges the ability of building owners to claim these sinks for their own decarbonization strategies, while carrying risks of material use.

Biogenic construction materials represent a far higher potential for carbon storage in buildings, including structural timber, straw, and biochar additives in concrete. Stakeholder perspectives diverge on the crediting of these temporary sinks, influenced by assumptions about long-term perspectives of the storage and end-of-life processes and technological advancements. Approaches applied range from no crediting to nearly full crediting under the expectation of future carbon capture solutions. Simplified methods, such as fixed-percentage allocation, coexist with complex dynamic modelling approaches that account for biomass regeneration and storage duration. Switzerland proposes a methodological pathway, to credit biogenic sinks when permanence is legally assured. This might be helpful to push the required technology development. While questions remain on the allocation of benefits between building owners, technology developers and end-of-life actors with carbon capture and storage.

Studies from the City of Zurich highlight the ecological relevance of cascade use of timber combining benefits of material substitution and energy use (Stadt Zurich, 2025). The study

shows also the shift in advantages over time and emphasize the strategic importance of advancing negative emission technologies.

Overall, the findings underscore the need for coherent regulation, transparent accounting rules, and cross-sectoral coordination to effectively use the mitigation potential of CO₂ sinks in the built environment while ensuring the long-term integrity and equitable attribution of stored carbon.

End-of-Life Strategies

Environmental Impacts Assessment of Photovoltaic Panel Waste Management in South Korea by LCA

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Abstract:

In recent decades, photovoltaic (PV) panel technology development has grown significantly around the world. As the demand for the installation of PV panel increases, high volume of PV waste is expected in the future. However, most LCA studies have often excluded the end-of-life (EoL) stage, mainly due to the low amount of PV panels that have reached the disposal stage so far. This study aims to assess the environmental impacts of the PV panel waste management practice in South Korea using the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology. Future waste quantities were projected through 2050 using the Population Balance Model (PBM) integrated with the Weibull function. Environmental impacts were analyzed using a “gate-to-gate” approach that included PV waste collection and transportation to a recycling plant, recycling processes, and residual waste disposal. The functional unit used is the recycling of 1,000 kg of c-Si PV panel waste. This study was performed using OpenLCA software v.2.6, with inventory datasets sourced from the Ecoinvent 3.11 database and complemented by primary data collected from domestic recycling facilities. Additional assumptions were also obtained from relevant literature. Impact assessment was conducted using the ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) method, which offers a comprehensive set of environmental impact categories. The overall climate change impact was quantified at approximately 404 kg CO₂-Eq, indicating that greenhouse gas emissions as one of the major contributors to the total environmental burden. The study highlights that the major contributors are related to the thermal treatment of the PV sandwich, followed by the energy consumption and transportation. However, energy recovery from the thermal process provides a notable offset benefit, reducing burdens in the overall impact categories. These findings provide valuable insights into the EoL stage of PV panels based on the South Korean perspective, which offers valuable insights into the country’s specific PV waste management practices and policy direction regarding the PV panel waste management system.

Closing the Loop for EV Batteries in Mexico: Integrating LCA and a Critically-Weighted Material Circularity Indicator

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Abstract:

Electromobility is scaling rapidly and pressuring supplies of critical minerals embedded in lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). In Mexico, where EV uptake is growing but end-of-life (EoL) governance remains nascent, evidence-based guidance is needed to prioritize circular strategies that simultaneously reduce environmental burdens and strengthen supply security. This study evaluates four EoL pathways for automotive LIBs—(i) controlled disposal, (ii) hydrometallurgical recycling, (iii) pyrometallurgical recycling, and (iv) stationary second-life reuse—using openLCA with ecoinvent 3.11 and IMPACT World+ for life-cycle assessment (LCA). The functional unit is one tonne of spent traction batteries, modeled for NMC and LFP chemistries under Mexican conditions. Circularity is quantified with the Material Circularity Indicator (MCI), extended in two ways that are pertinent to energy systems: (1) reactivating the utility factor to capture life-extension benefits of second life, and (2) introducing a criticality-weighted formulation that scales mass flows by mineral risk (e.g., Li, Co, Ni), thus aligning circularity scores with strategic supply considerations.

Results indicate second-life reuse yields the strongest combined performance when technically feasible, by displacing new cell production and extending service life; hydrometallurgy ranks next—especially for NMC—when lithium and cobalt are recovered at industrially representative yields; pyrometallurgy offers lower benefits given lithium losses and higher energy intensity; disposal is consistently worst. Sensitivity analyses demonstrate that Mexico's fossil-intensive grid materially influences recycling impacts, that transport distances and collection rates shape outcomes, and that recovery yields for lithium are decisive for both environmental and criticality-weighted circularity. The criticality extension notably reshapes the decision space: scenarios with similar total recovered mass diverge in priority when they differ in the recovery of high-risk minerals, favoring hydrometallurgical routes that capture lithium and cobalt over options that primarily recover base metals.

Key limitations include reliance on international inventory data for some unit processes, conservative assumptions about second-life eligibility and duration, and incomplete domestic statistics on flows of EoL batteries; these are addressed via transparent uncertainty ranges and scenario testing. Policy-relevant implications are threefold: (i) prioritize second-life deployment where safety and performance criteria are met; (ii) scale hydrometallurgical capacity with explicit lithium recovery targets; and (iii) implement producer-responsibility collection and digital traceability to enable a criticality-aware circular economy for EV batteries in Mexico. The combined LCA + critically-weighted MCI framework provides a practical decision tool for regulators and industry to align EoL choices with both environmental objectives and mineral security in the energy transition.

A Parameterised openLCA Model for Flexibly Assessing Lubricant Fate and Re-Refining Feasibility

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Abstract:

Lubricants keep industries in motion, both literally and figuratively. In industrial and transport systems, they reduce friction, wear and oxidation across a wide range of applications. In recent years, the lubricant industry has promoted the concept of “carbon handprints” to highlight the potential avoided emissions resulting from improved energy efficiency during use. However, these handprint claims often rely on narrow system boundaries that emphasise operational benefits while overlooking substantial lifecycle burdens. Losses during use, limited collection rates and the environmental impacts associated with waste lubricant oil (WLO) disposal remain significant challenges. Moreover, the end-of-life (EoL) stage, which ultimately determines whether resources can be recovered, receives comparatively little attention in industrial reporting.

This work links early lubricant design decisions to the formulation’s end-of-life (EoL) fate. It incorporates both initial formulation and use-phase changes, such as transformation and contamination, into a fully parameterised openLCA model of lubricant EoL pathways. Treatment options include re-refining, downcycling into low-grade fuels, energy recovery through combustion and hazardous-waste incineration. By integrating industrial data, regulations and re-refining requirements, the study identifies the chemical and physical properties most critical to consider at the design stage. Particular focus is placed on additive composition, contamination, flash-point changes and metal content, as these factors often determine whether a waste stream is technically and economically viable for re-refining.

A baseline model was developed to represent the pathway of a generic lubricant from the use-phase to EoL. Use-phase losses were quantified by major application categories and improper disposal routes, such as uncontrolled dumping or inefficient combustion, are included due to their impact on collectable WLO volumes and environmental burdens. The remaining properly collected fraction is then allocated to treatment routes reflecting average European practice. This baseline will be flexibly adjusted according to formulation-dependent constraints, enabling the exploration of how changes in additives, contamination, or physical properties may shift re-refining feasibility. The model is expected to highlight that formulation changes perceived as

environmentally positive, such as increasing the share of biobased synthetic base oils, may offer clear benefits during production and use, yet their altered chemical profiles can reduce the efficiency or even the viability of re-refining, highlighting important design trade-offs.

The results will highlight how formulation choices shape EoL pathways and demonstrate the importance of integrating life-cycle thinking into design-stage decisions. By moving beyond use-phase efficiency claims, this work will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the long-term environmental consequences of lubricant design.

Energy Systems

Improving the Integration of Electricity Generation in Life Cycle Assessment: A Case Study of Road Transportation in Canada.

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Abstract:

Electricity generation is responsible for a large share of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in most developed countries. The GHG-intensity of electricity is directly linked to the energy carriers and generators in a region's grid mix, with fossil generators leading to high emissions and renewable generators leading to low emissions. In line with this, governments in multiple developed countries are transitioning towards a fully renewable electric grid mix to meet their environmental impact reduction targets. With electricity generation being an important source of upstream emissions for multiple sectors, including the transportation, residential, and industrial sector, this transition towards carbon-free electricity will considerably impact the life cycle emissions of multiple products and processes. However, most previous life cycle assessment studies rely on spatially and temporally average emission factors to represent the GHG-intensity of electricity generation, missing spatiotemporal variations caused by the alternance of fossil and renewable generators in a region's grid mix. Multiple processes and products, such as electric vehicles, have a variable and controllable electricity demand and could benefit from these variations in GHG-intensity. In this work, we develop a life cycle assessment framework integrating the spatiotemporal variations in electricity generation, through regionalized hourly marginal emission factors, with OpenLCA background databases to model upstream emissions more accurately. We develop a representative model of the Canadian electricity system, built using Canadian electricity data and OpenLCA and optimized using the Python for Power System Analysis toolbox, which we then use to evaluate the GHG emissions of road passenger transportation in Canada. Our case study is tailored to the 13 provinces and territories in Canada (i.e., through regionalized charging patterns, driving conditions, temperature, etc.) to show the importance of integrating a high-resolution electricity generation model in life cycle assessment studies. Preliminary results show large spatial (i.e., across provinces and territories) and temporal (i.e., throughout the year) variations in the GHG-intensity of electricity generation in Canada, suggesting that average emission factors would not provide representative results. Our results also show that capturing these variations is essential to calculate the life cycle emissions of electric vehicles accurately. These conclusions prove the importance of integrating high-resolution electricity generation models into life cycle assessment frameworks to obtain accurate and representative results, which is further

confirmed and quantified by our case study of road transportation in Canada. Our framework could play a crucial role in the evaluation of electricity systems in Canada towards the country's GHGs reduction targets.

Green Hydrogen Production in Arid Regions: A Life Cycle Assessment of DAC-SOEC Integrated System

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Abstract:

The global demand for sustainable energy solutions has intensified the interest in green hydrogen production, particularly in regions with high renewable energy potential, such as those in Africa. However, water availability – a critical resource for electrolysis – can be a limiting factor in determining the geographical suitability for hydrogen production in these arid regions. Liquid solvent-based direct air capture (DAC) technology offers the potential to recover the water required for electrolysis from the air when coupled with high-temperature solid oxide electrolyzer cells (SOEC), addressing the issue of water availability. However, this integrated process remains relatively unexplored. Uncertainties remain concerning the intricacy of this production process route in relation to its potential environmental impacts. To address this gap, this research aims to assess the environmental impacts of green hydrogen produced in arid regions, specifically in Morocco and Senegal, including its transportation and subsequent injection into Germany's grid. These impacts are compared with those of the domestic hydrogen production process in Germany. We present the first cradle-to-gate life cycle assessment (LCA) following ISO 14040/44 standards to quantify the environmental impacts of the proposed integrated DAC-SOEC hydrogen production system to determine the most environmentally favorable import pathway. As expected, the use of renewable energy sources exerts the highest environmental influence within the system, followed by the transport stage, indicating that transport distance is a key factor in reducing overall impacts. These results underscore the importance of strategically selecting production locations to minimize environmental burdens. Furthermore, the integration of DAC can contribute to lower local water stress and provide a basis for policy recommendations aimed at scaling up green hydrogen infrastructure in water-scarce regions. This study supports the European Union's hydrogen strategy by demonstrating the potential of renewable hydrogen imports from water-scarce but energy-rich regions. The findings highlight how intercontinental cooperation in green hydrogen infrastructure can accelerate global decarbonization, strengthen Europe's energy security, and foster equitable partnerships driving the transition toward a sustainable and climate-neutral energy future.

Credible Environmental Footprinting of China's Provincial Power System Based on Best Available Evidence

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Abstract:

Accurate electricity environmental footprints (EEFs) are critical for China's decarbonization strategies and downstream supply chain management. While a substantial volume of accounting data currently exists in commercial databases and academic literature, credible EEFs for China remain hindered by four critical limitations. These include data opacity such as the absence of underlying data sources, coarse geographical and technological resolution that masks inter-provincial and sub-technology variations, insufficient local representativeness often caused by the reliance on foreign proxy data, and methodological flaws in multi-source integration which can lead to double counting.

To address these gaps, this study established a transparent framework based on the maximization of publicly available evidence. By rigorously screening high-quality unit process datasets from peer-reviewed literature, a novel multi-source integration strategy incorporating comprehensive batch modeling and Monte Carlo simulations was employed. This enabled the quantification of credible distribution ranges for the environmental footprints of 14 specific power generation technologies, alongside provincial environmental footprints for electricity generation and consumption (GEFs and CEFs) across 16 impact categories.

Results revealed a systematic overestimation of China's EEFs in mainstream commercial databases. Specifically, the derived carbon footprints of electricity consumption were 20–22% lower than values in ecoinvent and GaBi. This discrepancy was primarily attributed to the insufficient local representativeness of modern coal efficiency in external databases. Additionally, the transmission and distribution process proved to be a non-negligible contributor. It accounted for 3–15% of most impact categories and is notably higher for mineral resource depletion given the high material intensity of infrastructure. Furthermore, significant inter-provincial heterogeneity driven by resource endowments and technological choices was quantified. This revealed a distinct trade-off between decarbonization and mineral consumption in renewable-rich regions. These findings confirmed that only high-resolution accounting can resolve the critical disparities masked by conventional aggregated estimates.

Finally, this study identified specific scarcities of public unit process data for nuclear and natural gas power to guide future data development. Two key implications for China's energy transition were highlighted. First, the observed carbon-mineral trade-off necessitates a multi-dimensional assessment framework to prevent environmental burden shifting during the green transition. Second, the established high-resolution dataset provided a credible baseline for accurate downstream supply chain management and the effective navigation of international carbon trade barriers.

Evaluating the environmental impacts of direct air capture and storage in a renewable-rich industrial cluster: A case study of the Humber Industrial Cluster in the UK

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Abstract:

About 50.4% of energy generation in the United Kingdom (UK) in 2024 came from renewables, particularly offshore wind, contributing significantly to a record low average annual carbon intensity of 124 gCO₂eq/kWh. The operational capacity of offshore wind in the UK is projected to increase from 16 to 50 gigawatts by 2030. However, energy curtailment remains a huge challenge for offshore wind farm operators, with curtailed energy increasing from 6.3 GWh (2013) to 4,930 GWh (2024).

The Humber region is the energy estuary of the UK with a strong presence of offshore wind farms, but on the other hand, it is the highest-emitting industrial cluster, accounting for one-third of UK industrial CO₂ emissions. Most of these emissions come from hard-to-abate sources such as maritime and road transport, petrochemicals, and steelmaking. Capturing residual CO₂ emissions from these sectors is practically infeasible with Point Source Carbon Capture (PSCC) methods; therefore, integrating Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) technologies such as Direct Air Carbon Capture and Storage (DACCS) is imperative.

DAC is modular and scalable with the flexibility to be sited anywhere. However, for optimal performance, efficient resource utilisation and cost reduction, proximity to renewable energy sources and shared decarbonisation infrastructure are crucial. To estimate the environmental impacts of the integration of offshore wind with DAC in the Humber, a life cycle assessment of a fast swing solid sorbent DAC system, including CO₂ transport and storage, is conducted in this study. The carbon emissions over the duration of the DACCS system's operational lifetime are estimated. Two sources of electricity (offshore wind and grid) and four heat sources (waste heat, heat pump, hydrogen, and natural gas) are modelled to assess the feasibility and system performance based on the carbon removal efficiency (CRE).

Our results show that the CRE ranges between 67–92% for grid-connected configurations and 71–97% for offshore wind-connected configurations. DACCS paired with offshore wind and

waste heat offers the best CRE of 97% with a corresponding environmental performance of 32.8 kgCO₂eq/tCO₂ removed. Siting DAC in the Humber industrial cluster offers the opportunity for CO₂ captured on site to be transported using the proposed onshore and offshore pipelines to the Northern Endurance saline aquifer for permanent storage. The waste heat potential in the region is substantial and can be utilised to satisfy the heat requirements of the DAC system.

Keywords: direct air capture, offshore wind, carbon emissions

Comparative LCA of hydrogen production pathways

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Abstract:

Hydrogen is increasingly recognized as a key energy carrier for enabling deep decarbonization across multiple sectors, but its overall sustainability strongly depends on the production pathway employed [1]. A comparative Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is conducted using OpenLCA software based on the Ecoinvent 3.11 database, to assess the environmental performance of three major hydrogen production pathways, which include the conventional fossil fuel-based Steam Methane Reforming (SMR) against Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis (PEMWE) and Alkaline Water Electrolysis (AWE). The analysis is carried out with both electrolytic systems powered by onshore wind electricity. Since the three technologies deliver hydrogen at different outlet pressures, a common storage stage is included; therefore, the functional unit is defined as 1 kg of hydrogen produced and stored at 30 bar.

Results show that SMR from fossil natural gas remains the most carbon-intensive pathway, with a climate change impact of 11.35 kg CO₂-eq per kg of hydrogen produced, while PEMWE and AWE achieve substantially lower emissions at 2.38 kg CO₂-eq/kg H₂ and 3.43 kg CO₂-eq/kg H₂, respectively. These values represent approximately an 80% reduction for PEMWE and a 70% reduction for AWE compared to SMR. Similar trends are observed for other impact categories, such as non-renewable energy use. Electrolysis routes, however, exhibit higher impacts in acidification, eutrophication, and material resource use. These burdens are primarily linked to renewable electricity generation and the material requirements of electrolyzer stacks. While AWE relies heavily on nickel and steel, PEMWE depends on scarce metals such as platinum and titanium, resulting in material resource impacts roughly an order of magnitude higher than SMR. Water use patterns also vary with PEMWE benefits from lower water demand, whereas AWE shows the highest due to its electrolyte requirements.

Results also confirm that electricity for electrolysis dominates most impact categories, accounting for more than 75% of total impacts in PEMWE and about 45% in AWE. In AWE, stack and balance-of-plant manufacturing constitute a more relevant share of impacts, reflecting its higher material intensity.

Overall, the comparison highlights the clear climate and energy advantages of wind-powered electrolysis over fossil-based production, with PEMWE demonstrating the most favorable overall performance despite its reliance on critical raw materials.

[1] Bhandari, R., Trudewind, C. A., & Zapp, P., "Life cycle assessment of hydrogen production via electrolysis – a review," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, pp. 151-163, 2014.

Environmental Life Cycle Assessment of Hydrogen and Electric Road Mobility in the EU

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Abstract:

The decarbonization of the mobility sector in the EU is a crucial objective of the European Green Deal, aiming for a 90% reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2050. Achieving this goal requires the transition toward Electric Vehicles (EVs) and renewable or low-carbon fuels such as hydrogen [1]. This study aims to investigate the full life-cycle environmental impacts of electric and hydrogen-based road transport and comparing them with conventional diesel-based mobility.

Two comparative Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) case studies are examined, using OpenLCA software based on the Ecoinvent v3.11 database. For light-duty mobility (passenger cars), Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) fueled by renewable hydrogen are evaluated against Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) and Internal Combustion Engine Vehicles (ICEVs), with the functional unit defined as one kilometer driven per vehicle. For heavy-duty transport, fuel cell heavy-duty trucks fueled by renewable hydrogen are compared with conventional diesel trucks (functional unit: tonne-kilometer).

Using the Environmental Footprint (EF) v3.1 method, the results show that the climate change impact for the passenger cars depends strongly on the electricity source. While BEVs outperform all other technologies when powered exclusively by renewable electricity, the FCEVs fueled by renewable hydrogen - where hydrogen is produced via an electrolyzer directly connected to a wind turbine - have lower global warming impacts than BEVs charged with grid electricity

For heavy-duty vehicles, the climate change impact of a fuel cell truck fueled by renewable hydrogen is 0.016 kg CO₂-eq per tonne-kilometer, nearly 85% lower than the climate change impact of the diesel truck which stands at 0.102 kg CO₂-eq per tonne-kilometer. Moreover, the operation phase of the fuel cell truck, which includes renewable hydrogen production and use, contributes approximately 75% to climate change and energy resource use, and around 55% to acidification and eutrophication.

Overall, the findings support the EU mobility strategy, suggesting that the transition from diesel trucks to fuel cell heavy-duty trucks powered by renewable hydrogen can reduce climate change impacts by 85%. Furthermore, the results suggest that the decarbonization of the passenger car sector can be done by using BEVs, but first requires the decarbonization of the electricity sector.

References:

[1] European Commission, Directorate General for Mobility and Transport (2021) Sustainable and smart mobility strategy.

Life Cycle Assessment of Ground-Mounted PV Power Plants With and Without Battery Energy Storage Systems in France: Substitution Effects, Operational Shifting, and Infrastructure Synergies

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Abstract:

The deployment of ground-mounted photovoltaic (PV) power plants in France is expanding rapidly as part of national and European decarbonisation strategies. In parallel, Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) are increasingly considered to address challenges related to variability, curtailment and grid congestion. Beyond operational advantages, storage may also influence the environmental performance of PV systems by shifting electricity injection to periods characterised by higher marginal impacts. However, these potential benefits must be balanced against the environmental burdens associated with battery manufacturing, operation and end-of-life. To contribute to this discussion, this presentation aims to present a comparative Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) study conducted of PV plants with and without co-located BESS, evaluating both present-day and future-year configurations.

The study follows ISO 14040/44 principles and models representative French ground-mounted PV plants in two configurations: a conventional PV system without storage, and a PV system equipped with 24-hour operational BESS. Temporal generation and injection models were developed to estimate when electricity is delivered to the grid, enabling the identification of the substituted marginal electricity mix for each hour. Annual substituted mixes were created based on electricity price-driven scenarios that reflect the technologies operating at the margin. Forward-looking scenarios for 2030 to 2050 were also constructed to capture the progressive decarbonisation of the French power system. The LCA includes infrastructure-sharing effects and accounts for avoided PV production losses due to storage.

BESS-equipped PV plants systematically substitute a more carbon-intensive marginal mix than conventional PV systems, as shifted electricity is injected during periods of higher marginal emissions. However, this does not always compensate for burdens associated with battery construction, operation and end-of-life, depending on the impact category studied. In long-term scenarios, the substitution benefit declines as the French marginal mix becomes progressively

less carbon-intensive. By 2050, the environmental advantage of shifting is significantly reduced due to increased penetration of low-carbon and renewable technologies.

Co-located PV-BESS systems can provide short- and medium-term environmental benefits in France by aligning injections with higher-emission periods and by rationalising infrastructure. However, these benefits diminish in highly decarbonised future contexts.

Further research should examine alternative storage configurations, sensitivity to BESS capacity, and comparisons with non-co-located PV and BESS installations to better understand trade-offs between enhanced shifting potential and increased storage-related impacts.

Iterative Life Cycle Assessment: Methodology for Resolving the Carbon Intensity of Self-Consuming Products

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Abstract:

Recursive, self-consuming products within complex industrial systems pose a challenge in life cycle assessment, particularly in estimating and evaluating the carbon intensity (CI) of fuels produced and later consumed on site. Refining systems exemplify this difficulty: intermediate streams (including hydrogen streams) are repeatedly transformed, combusted, and/or reintroduced, creating circular dependencies that complicate both inventory construction and impact allocation.

This work presents a generalized methodological framework for resolving CI in systems where products partially fuel their own production. Two components are emphasized. First, we develop an iterative stream-level CI determination method capable of converging on stable carbon intensities for interdependent material and energy flows. Second, we introduce an allocation procedure for self-consuming products, enabling practitioners to quantify how much of a given stream (e.g., hydrogen) is required to produce additional units of itself versus other coproducts. This distinction is increasingly important under emerging policy regimes—such as production-based clean fuel incentives—which require verifiable accounting of internal consumption pathways.

The proposed framework was developed with learnings from performing a commercial LCA that came across these challenges. It is demonstrated using a representative system boundary and anonymized flow structure constructed to preserve client confidentiality while illustrating the methodological advances. The approach is software-agnostic and can be implemented in LCA environments that support iterative calculation.

More broadly, the methodology offers a replicable strategy for CI estimation in any industrial network with recursive flows, contributing new tools for transparent and policy-relevant carbon accounting.

Innovation in LCA

Data Creation

LLMs4LCA: Large-Language Model-Powered Structured Output Generation for the Harmonization of Life Cycle Assessment Studies

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Abstract:

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a valuable tool for the evaluation of the environmental impact of products, but it experiences some inherent problems. For example, data collection is highly labor-intensive. The scope of LCA studies is at times too narrow, and in other cases, the level of inventory data is not sufficiently detailed. Finally, it is difficult to compare studies due to differences in data collection, modelling, and calculation methods.

Artificial intelligence (AI) and, more recently, large language models (LLMs), have demonstrated potential for improving LCA quality and scalability. However, their use cases are mostly context-specific and dependent on input data quality. This study represents a first step towards building a customisable, domain-agnostic structured output generation (SOG) LLM-leveraged data pipeline for the extraction, harmonisation, and calculation of LCA inventory inputs from published studies. Concretely, we propose an algorithm for automatic extraction of inventory data and system characterisation metadata from LCA papers and compare it to a manually curated dataset.

The method was applied to a use case of dairy LCA studies. The model automatically extracted and harmonised unstructured data from 39 studies to a manually configured data structure of 107 fields (e.g., Study Details, Inventory inputs, Midpoint Indicators). Results were then compared to a manually created dairy LCI dataset using the same papers, and the similarity of results was analysed, showing a mean similarity score of 0.75. As a next step, by connecting to an LCA software programmatically, the results of the SOG pipeline can be automatically mapped to inventory processes from a background dataset (e.g., Ecoinvent), and used for the standardised recalculation of midpoint indicators using the same database version, applying the same calculation methods and automated mapping assumptions.

By combining LLMs and traditional data science techniques, this study aims to provide an alternative to conducting heavy manual LCA research, thus enabling automated literature

reviews and comparative studies. The use of this pipeline can potentially save hundreds of hours of an LCA researcher's manual labor.

Toward Scalable LCA Inventories: An End-to-End Automated Pipeline for Converting Heterogeneous Technical Narratives into Standardized Process Data

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Abstract:

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) fundamentally relies on high-fidelity process data, yet a substantial portion of the information required for inventory modelling remains embedded in unstructured scientific literature and technical reports. Converting these heterogeneous narratives into structured Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) datasets has traditionally depended on expert-driven manual curation—an approach that ensures methodological rigor but is inherently resource-intensive and difficult to scale. This work presents a methodological transition toward the automated, standards-oriented reconstruction of process-level LCI datasets, addressing the critical bottleneck of data availability.

The core contribution of this study is a robust workflow for LCI dataset creation and validation that automates the cognitive tasks traditionally performed by domain experts. Rather than focusing on simple text extraction, our approach emphasizes the reconstruction of unit process logic. By employing an autonomous agent integrated with a domain-specific Model Context Protocol (MCP), the system mimics the expert's validation process: it does not just "read" text, but dynamically cross-references extracted technical parameters against established nomenclature and flow properties to ensure data consistency.

The study focuses on overcoming two primary challenges in automated dataset creation: completeness and standardization. First, the system parses unstructured process descriptions to identify system boundaries and reference flows, extracting quantitative exchanges (inputs/outputs) while performing automated mass balance checks to flag inconsistencies. Second, standardization is enforced via TIDAS (Tiangong DAta System)—an ISO/ILCD-compliant infrastructure designed to bridge legacy compliance with modern AI efficiency. Utilizing this framework as a quality gate, the extracted data is mapped to structured formats compliant with international standards. This research demonstrates that AI-assisted

workflows can produce high-quality, transparent datasets that are comparable to manually curated versions, offering a viable solution to rapidly expand the coverage of LCA databases.

From Data Gaps to Interoperability: The ORCHESTER Data Ecosystem

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Abstract:

Reliable Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) data is essential for robust sustainability assessments, yet data gaps and format incompatibilities frequently undermine Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) results. A recent review found that over 55% of 285 reviewed LCA case studies lacked complete description of data collection [1]. Another article mentioned that about 70% shared inventory data are provided only in PDF or DOC formats, which strongly limited the data accessibility and reusability [2]. At the same time, LCI data are derived from a variety of sources, including experimental results, process parameters, and simulations across complex value chains. To address this, in the Fraunhofer Flagship project ORCHESTER, we propose a user-friendly yet comprehensive data ecosystem approach designed to accelerate assessments and support material innovation.

The ORCHESTER ecosystem [3] connects heterogeneous materials, processes, and assessment data through ontology-based integration and AI-supported analytics. Within the ORCHESTER project, we integrate multiple dimensions - from material properties, process parameters to sustainability indicators. In this presentation, we demonstrate how the Orchester ecosystem could bring benefits to sustainability assessment through a practical use case on rare-earth permanent magnets. Ultimately, ORCHESTER aims to deliver multiple digital products such as criticality radar to accelerate the material development. In addition to material and process characteristics, customers receive sustainability performance indicators for their products that not only quantify their carbon footprint, but also the energy consumption, resource intensity, resource criticality, ethical responsibility, and resilience of the value chain, making customers' products future-proof.

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LCI Databases

BAFU:2025: open-access cross-sectoral life-cycle inventory database

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Abstract:

Two parallel trends are emerging in the creation of life-cycle inventory (LCI) databases. On the one hand, various stakeholders are active on the market with commercial databases that are either cross-sectoral (e.g. ecoinvent, Sphera) or sector-specific (e.g. Agrifootprint). In addition, there are activities for sector-specific databases that are available free of charge as add-ons to commercial databases (e.g. Agribalyse). To our knowledge, there has been so far no up-to-date, disaggregated cross-sectoral open-access LCI database. The LCI database of the Swiss Federal Administration, BAFU:2025 can close this gap.

The BAFU:2025 database contains LCI data on products and processes in the fields of construction/housing, mobility/transport, energy, metals, chemicals, paper and pulp, agriculture and food, consumption, waste treatment and disposal. The 2025 version currently contains around 11,000 LCIs, divided into 176 categories (energy, transport, materials, etc.). The FOEN and partners regularly update the data and create new data in line with current technological developments that require life cycle assessment (LCA) information.

The LCI data is transmitted in ecospold V1 format. This format enables the provision of software-independent information. The data can be reused in various LCA software and with Python or R calculation scripts.

The LCI were created on behalf of the Swiss Federal Administration and comply with the FOEN data quality guideline DQRv2:2023. Most LCI have undergone critical review to verify their compatibility with ISO 14'040 and DQRv2:2023. All basic information is available in reports to ensure the transparency of the information provided. All newly developed LCI will be evaluated through a critical review process.

The Swiss Federal Administration makes its LCI data available free of charge, thereby fulfilling the required transparency in the area of LCA on the one hand and the Swiss Federal Administration's open government strategy on the other. It supports the application of laws and ordinances without commercial dependent to an external database. In addition, it can be used

in free online LCA-calculators. Finally, the developed data shall not be resold, and the source of the data must be indicated.

The Swiss Federal Administration will continue to develop actively the database with partners in a continuous improvement process. Other communication formats are also considered to create machine-readable datasets.

Important note to the organisers of the OpenLCA-Conference 2026: we can only make a final decision on whether we can give the presentation after the database has been published.

Building Regionalized Unit-Process Inventories for Emerging Economies: A Practical Example for LCI Dataset Creation and Validation

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Abstract:

Environmental assessments of energy-intensive industries rely heavily on life cycle inventory datasets. Beyond being data-intensive, their robustness depends on the quality, origin, and representativeness of the underlying information. Although new approaches for dataset development have emerged, most environmental assessments still depend on conventional generic datasets that reflect European or North American background conditions. For energy-intensive value chains in the global south, this practice leads to systematic misrepresentation.

The objective of this work was to generate a coherent and transparent set of regionalized unit process inventories for electricity, fossil fuels, biofuels, biogas or biomethane, and selected chemical intermediates. These inventories replace generic datasets with parameters sourced directly from publicly available national planning documents, industrial statistics, industrial input, and technology studies. The approach maintains methodological alignment with LCA methodology and standards while ensuring that regional characteristics are accurately reflected.

A central methodological challenge concerns the regionalization of life cycle inventory datasets in a manner that captures local energy mixes, biofuel technologies, residue-based feedstocks, and logistics patterns, while remaining consistent with the structure of the global pathway literature. To address this, the study develops a structured set of LCI building blocks for key background systems, using the chemical industry in an emerging economy as a case study.

The methodological workflow translates national-level data into inventory-ready unit processes, with explicit definitions of process inputs, energy carriers, residue handling, emission factors, and co-product allocation rules. Harmonization procedures ensured cross-dataset compatibility by aligning functional units, temporal boundaries, and allocation principles, and by cross-checking with regionalized industrial statistics. Validation involved triangulation across multiple local data sources and checks with regional experts for completeness, thermodynamic plausibility, and consistency with mass and energy balances.

The resulting regionalized datasets diverge substantially from global defaults. Electricity inventories reflect national energy mixes; biofuel datasets incorporate country-specific yields, mechanization levels, and vinasse management practices; and biomethane inventories reflect agricultural and agro-industrial specific practices. When applied to technology pathway modelling, generic datasets meaningfully alter comparative outcomes, affecting estimated emissions, low emissions technology availability, and economic competitiveness. The results demonstrate that reliance on non-regional datasets would misrepresent both the mitigation potential and the system-level enablers required for climate-neutral transitions in the global south.

An atomic LCA data space for mapping and LCA reference data management

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Abstract:

Mapping of LCA systems, i.e. assigning elements from one system to elements of another system, has since long been a topic in LCA. The need for mapping arises from existing different LCA system nomenclatures and concepts, with differing flow names, compartment structures, etc..

Problems in mapping come from differing levels of granularity (surface water vs lake and river), lack of specificity (organic chemicals, as flow), and different concepts in LCA systems (land transformation from one state to another modeled in one or two flows), for example. Some time ago, a major international collaboration effort in UN GLAD led to the publication of a concept and of mapping files for major LCA systems. The concept can be characterised as classic: pairs for mapped elements are proposed, together with an indication of the mapping quality.

We present a different approach by use of a graph database, where hierarchies and multi-dimensional relations can be modeled directly. Basically, main elements of main LCA reference systems are modeled in an interconnected graph. Each element in a LCA reference system is broken down to its smallest unit, called atom, connected with polymorphic relations to other elements. This allows to directly reflect different structures and concepts in reference systems. This system can be used for reference data management, and also for "translating" elements from one system another, i.e. for a mapping.

in the presentation, we will shortly introduce mapping principles, then introduce the atomic LCA data space, and show its application for mapping SimaPro to openLCA reference data, and for the management of the reference data of the MSDB database.

Developing MexiLCA: An Open Mexican Life Cycle Inventory Database for Enhanced Regional Sustainability Assessment

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Abstract:

The development of high-quality, region-specific life cycle inventory (LCI) data remains one of the major limitations for conducting robust Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). Although global LCI databases have matured, Mexico still lacks an openly accessible repository that reflects its national production systems, technologies, and environmental conditions. This gap restricts the accuracy of LCAs used for public policy, industrial decision-making, and academic research. In response, this work presents MexiLCA, an emerging open LCI database that compiles Mexican-specific datasets and is fully compatible with openLCA through a transparent JSON structure.

The objective of this initiative is to create and consolidate a set of high-quality unit process datasets representing key economic sectors in Mexico. To date, approximately 150 datasets have been developed following the CREA framework (Construction, Resources/Energy, Environment, and Agriculture). The data sources primarily include LCAs from national research projects, peer-reviewed scientific articles, and master's and doctoral theses conducted in Mexico over the last ten years. These sources provide detailed, context-rich information that strengthens the representativeness of local processes.

The methodology integrates: (1) a standardized data template aligned with openLCA and ILCD recommendations; and (2) automated processing tools designed to convert raw information into structured JSON datasets. This semi-automated pipeline accelerates dataset creation while ensuring sufficient documentation and interoperability. Work is ongoing to continue validating the datasets to ensure completeness, plausibility, internal consistency, and metadata quality.

Preliminary results indicate that MexiLCA is being successfully tested in various national LCA projects across sectors such as construction materials, waste management, and agri-food systems. Based on insights from existing literature, the use of localized datasets is expected to generate significant variations in environmental impact results compared with those obtained using foreign proxy data. These anticipated differences emphasize the importance of developing regionally representative inventories to support Mexico's sustainability goals,

including decarbonization pathways, circular economy strategies, and environmentally informed policy design.

MexiLCA will continue expanding through the automated integration workflow, with future efforts focused on incorporating additional sectors and refining dataset quality. The initiative contributes to global advances in transparent, high-quality dataset creation and offers a replicable model for developing open, country-specific LCI databases.

From Data Availability to Data Usability: How AI Is Transforming Chinese LCA Database

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Abstract:

Global life cycle assessment (LCA) practice increasingly relies on background data that can be accessed, interpreted, and connected across different regions and database systems. As China becomes deeply embedded in global supply chains, the demand for credible Chinese background data in global LCA models has grown rapidly. Although high-quality Chinese background datasets are emerging, their effective use still requires substantial expertise in data discovery, methodological interpretation, and cross-database alignment. Existing databases also exhibit heterogeneity in process coverage, metadata completeness, methodological assumptions, and impact assessment settings. Such heterogeneity makes it challenging to identify appropriate datasets, understand their methodological context, and align data from multiple sources within a single model, which limits the contribution of background databases to LCA-based decision support. To address these limitations, there is a need for approaches that enhance the usability of Chinese LCA data and support interoperable information exchange.

This study presents an implemented AI-enabled LCA data infrastructure that aims to improve the usability, transparency, and interoperability of Chinese background data in global LCA practice. The approach combines expert knowledge, semantic representations of LCA datasets, and embeddings trained across several databases. The system operates not as a generative model that invents new values but as an intelligence layer grounded in verified LCA databases. Three main capabilities are demonstrated:

(1) Semantic retrieval across Chinese and international databases. Natural-language queries are mapped to process metadata and flow structures, enabling users to identify relevant Chinese datasets and compare them with corresponding entries in other databases.

(2) Expert-informed background data matching and analytical reasoning. Embeddings informed by expert rules, multi-database sources, and process semantics support the selection of suitable background datasets and produce recommendations that reflect expert judgment on technological relevance, representativeness, and methodological consistency. Each recommendation is traceable and linked to its underlying data sources.

(3) Cross-database comparison and methodological interpretation. Differences between Chinese datasets and international databases in product category, representativeness, and impact indicators such as GWP are identified and explained, facilitating understanding of methodological differences and supporting consistent integration within global LCA frameworks.

These capabilities demonstrate how an implemented and validated research approach can improve the usability of LCA background data across databases. By enhancing accessibility, methodological clarity, and cross-database interpretation, the approach supports more transparent and interoperable data use in global LCA and contributes to the broader goal of trustworthy data sharing and connectivity across the international LCA community.

openLCA Tools and Integration: Lessons Learned and Shared Experiences

NearUser LCA – a LCA tool for process specialists

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Abstract:

Material and process development is facing increasing demand to demonstrate the sustainability of proposed measures. For well-known standard processes and process routes, it is advantageous that process engineers without specialized LCA knowledge can evaluate the environmental impact of process changes independently. This is achieved by combining a fully parameterized LCA model hosted on an OpenLCA IPC server with a custom HMI based on the web-based platform PhysicsWorks.

Establishing the parameterized LCA model requires extensive collaboration with process engineers to extract the necessary inventory data. Therefore, the facilities have to be equipped with data logging devices. These inventory data are introduced as parameters into the LCA model. A Python script in the PhysicsWorks framework extracts the inputs from the input mask. Then, it allocates them to the corresponding model parameters and initiates the calculation on the IPC server. After calculation, the impact categories are displayed in the results window. Since the parameters of the model vary from one investigated process to another, each process (route) requires its own main script, which remains easily accessible through the PhysicsWorks solver architecture. The solvers can be selected in parallel by the single LCA module in PhysicsWorks.

In this work, the procedure is demonstrated at the manufacturing of aluminium semi-finished parts. Further activities concern the integration of this procedure into the LKR dataspace, where the relevant model parameters of each process setup are directly extracted from digital process data. This enables a quick evaluation of development activities with respect to their environmental impact.

Integrating LCA data into product development: A Python-driven workflow leveraging openLCA as calculation backend

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Abstract:

A novel LCI modelling framework and Python-based calculation tool were developed to facilitate the integration of LCA into product development processes. The framework implements a standardized data format, where systems are modelled as modular data blocks following a system-assembly-component hierarchy. Each module can be linked to scenario-, region-, or design-based variation parameters to explore different system versions and assumptions throughout the different stages of product development. As a result of data modularity, it is possible to substitute or adjust individual modules without affecting the rest of the system, enabling fast reconfiguration of design variants and reuse of product data within engineering workflows. The linked hierarchy, in turn, makes it possible to aggregate and analyze results on different levels.

After LCI modelling, the Python-based calculation model is used to transform the standardized data into actionable insights. First, a connection is established with openLCA through the IPC tool, using which impact factors are extracted for every process present in the LCI, and stored locally. Next, the impact factors are used to calculate results for each unique combination of the modelled scenario-, region-, and design variations, representing every possible system version. Results for each system version are stored in a single, exhaustive result table alongside variation tags, serving as primary input to the generation of an extensive, interactive impact report.

The impact report allows users to filter and compare system versions, drill down from system- to assembly- and component level, and explore the influence of scenario, regional, or design-based variation on key impact categories. It offers a wide range of result visualizations with different levels of complexity, from high-level summaries for managers to more detailed breakdowns for engineers and LCA experts - ensuring results are tailored to the needs of different product development stakeholders. The report is generated as a browser-based dashboard that can be shared internally via a link, making it easy to distribute, review, and discuss results across teams.

Overall, the approach combines the flexibility of Python-based calculation and visualization with the robust calculation backend and database access of openLCA, enabling efficient exploration of LCA results within product development workflows.

System dynamics and LCA – Current implementation in openLCA

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Abstract:

Over the years, LCA has proven itself as a powerful tool for assessing the sustainability of product systems. Nevertheless, key aspects of sustainability, such as thresholds and dynamic system behaviour, are mostly ignored in LCA. LCA recommendations are therefore based on a narrow system view and thus, provide decision-makers with incomplete information. System dynamics (SD) has been discussed as an approach that can enable a wider system view and, with linking this to LCA, can overcome some of the mentioned limitations.

Several published case studies have now demonstrated its usefulness [1, 2]. Linking SD models to LCA models allows the inclusion of planetary boundaries, the dynamics of a product system's contextual environmental as well as the element of time. Yet, the use of two separate software and the manual transfer of SD to LCA data or vice versa makes it a time-consuming task for modellers. Therefore, a SD feature has now been implemented in openLCA.

It allows SD and LCA practitioners to import their SD models in the XMILE format into openLCA. A separate SD model editor enables one to define model settings, such as simulation length and delta time, select an impact assessment method, as well as view the SD model in a simplified graphical editor. In the calculation set up, model variables (stocks, rates, auxiliaries) can be linked to parameters of selected LCA product systems. The modeller can then run a simulation. In each simulation step, it will then calculate the linked product system with the respective values from the system dynamics model of that step. A results page will then show life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) results for each simulation step which can be exported to excel with the corresponding model variables. This is the first software solution that allows one to link LCA models to SD models, making it possible to calculate dynamic impact results over time.

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Making LCA easier: onlineLCA as a tool to bring LCA expertise into enterprise workflows

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Abstract:

The need of calculating the environmental impacts of products is increasing due to current regulatory requirements. Standards like EN15804, DPPs, CBAM are making LCA more and more important for enterprises, and therefore increasing the need for tools that allow to easily and quickly perform such studies. At the same time, many available LCA tools are mainly designed for expert use, which limits the autonomy of other actors involved. In fact, ensuring compliance with environmental standards and tracking the impacts of products requires the involvement of multiple departments, including product development, procurement, higher management and more.

The idea behind onlineLCA stems from these requirements. It is a webtool developed by GreenDelta to allow non-LCA-experts to perform mass-calculations of LCAs through an intuitive interface. Users can interact with the model, for example modifying parameters, and obtain results without needing in-depth knowledge of LCA modelling. This allows many people in an organization, independent of their level of expertise, to explore different variants and options securely, fast, and correctly.

More than two years after its first release, onlineLCA continues to evolve. The latest major update is the introduction of the “form editor”. This feature allows administrators to create new forms that guide users more easily in providing the required information such as quantities of materials, transportation distances or country of production. It makes possible to create a questionnaire-style form, hide certain entries from the end-user view or make them read-only.

The form editor represents another step towards the goal of making onlineLCA intuitive yet flexible and adaptable to users’ needs, and ultimately of making LCA more approachable.

Social LCA Case Studies

Methodological improvements for S-LCA in openLCA through sectoral product segmentation: Application to methanol production

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Abstract:

Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) still has limited practical application compared with environmental LCA, particularly in complex industrial value chains [1]. This work introduces a reproducible S-LCA framework tailored to the chemical sector, applied to a hypothetical conventional thermochemical production of methanol in Spain. The framework is designed to support cradle-to-grave assessment; however, when the use and end-of-life stages cannot be evaluated, the scope is constrained to cradle-to-gate system boundary.

The main contribution of this work is the improvement of product-level segmentation within economic sectors by explicitly documenting the workflow in openLCA, thereby enabling more transparent and comparable social assessments [2]. The product system is constructed by integrating process inventory data with worker-hour requirements, and the process network (natural gas reforming, synthesis and utilities) is modelled by assigning process-specific labour parameters [2].

For the development and characterization of the social risk assessment, the study relies on both the social-risk oriented PSILCA database and the environmental LCA database ecoinvent, together with its SOCA add-on. While SOCA helps ensure consistency between the social and environmental dimensions of the LCA, whereas PSILCA cannot always guarantee this, as it product systems do not necessarily match those represented in ecoinvent.

The methodology details a practical S-LCA workflow for product segmentation in openLCA. Key steps include: (i) treating worker hours as activity variables to facilitate scenario scaling; (ii) integrating labour intensities throughout the supply chain; (iii) aggregating risks using the Social Impacts Weighting Method to identify priority hotspots; and (iv) performing sensitivity analyses with varying cut-off values and data-quality settings to account for their influence on system completeness.

The results focus on three UNEP/SETAC-aligned indicators [3], prioritized for their relevance in chemical industries [4]: Health & Safety (Workers), Weekly Working Hours per Employee, and Child Labour.

Acknowledgments

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Social risks in circular textile transitions: Combining site-specific and generic S-LCA for fibre-to-fibre recycling between Europe and global supply chains

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Abstract:

Circular textile strategies, including fibre-to-fibre (FTF) recycling, are vital to the European efforts to manage the environmental burden of post-consumer textile waste. However, the social implications of these strategies and their potential to mitigate or redistribute social risks along global value chains remain poorly understood. In this study, we report the results of a site-specific and generic Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) study undertaken to analyse the social risks and opportunities associated with an EU-based FTF chemical recycling model for discarded textile waste.

The assessment, conducted within the EU-funded Textile Recycling Excellence (T-REX) project, used primary data from collection, sorting, recycling, and yarn-spinning organizations operating across six European countries. Social performance was evaluated using a reference-scale approach, comparing site-specific indicators against global or national reference points from the UN Human Rights Commission, the ILO, and related institutions. Generic data from the PSILCA database were applied to upstream stages of textile production to contextualize the T-REX model within global production networks.

The site-specific assessment identified elevated risks in 10 of 25 subcategories, particularly gender disparities, wages, and local employment quality. Stakeholders generally welcomed the structured visibility offered by S-LCA but highlighted challenges in reporting sensitive data, interpreting indicator thresholds, and ensuring consistent data availability across countries. The generic assessment confirmed that major social hotspots persist in fibre cultivation and garment manufacturing in non-EU regions, where structural governance issues dominate risk profiles. Together, the results show that while scaling FTF recycling in Europe can support improved local working conditions, it cannot, on its own, address entrenched upstream inequalities.

Methodologically, the study illustrates the value of combining site-specific and generic S-LCA for critically interpreting circular transitions, revealing risk redistribution patterns and gaps in

existing indicator sets. Building on these findings, the upcoming EU project CellFil will extend this work by further developing S-LCA approaches for emerging circular textile systems, addressing identified data limitations, and integrating stakeholder-driven indicators into new fibre-to-fibre value chains.

The work thus contributes practical lessons for applying S-LCA in real-world circular textile initiatives and for designing socially just governance strategies in the European circular economy.

Combining Social Acceptance and Social Life Cycle Assessment? A case study within PSILCA

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Abstract:

Social acceptance plays a crucial role in the successful market integration of energy technologies, and even more in addressing the needs and expectations of stakeholders. A wide range of factors can influence their acceptance, such as perceived benefits and risks. Although social acceptance is a social topic, it is not yet included in established Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) references, e.g. ISO 14075, the UNEP guidelines, nor in the Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment Database (PSILCA).

While it might be reasonable to analyze social acceptance and S-LCA separately, it could also be advantageous to link them. A literature review showed different approaches regarding the connection between the two topics. Some authors integrate social acceptance into S-LCA in the form of impact categories, subcategories or indicators while others treat social acceptance solely as a rationale for conducting S-LCA studies. A third group does not establish any connection between the two.

In this study, several approaches for connecting social acceptance and S-LCA are proposed in addition to those identified in the literature. These are evaluated through a case study.

S-LCA can serve as a secondary data source for analyzing social acceptance. For example, if the health impact on workers is a factor influencing acceptance, this information can be taken from S-LCA results, e.g. generated with PSILCA. Additionally, S-LCA can support independent opinion formation for individuals by providing a source of information. A potential challenge lies in translating PSILCA results into a form that is comprehensive for a broad audience, including the local community, society and social science researchers.

Vice versa, the integration of social acceptance analysis into S-LCA can be another beneficial option. As identified in literature, social flows, e.g. different indicators for the factors influencing social acceptance within an impact category “social acceptance”, could be added to PSILCA within own models. In this way, S-LCA can be complemented with an additional social topic.

Preliminary results from a case study show that existing PSILCA subcategories and indicators do not fully correspond to the factors influencing social acceptance, e.g., of direct air capture technologies. While new indicators can be integrated with primary data, complementing them with generic data, e.g. for the background system, remains a major challenge.

Advancing Social Life Cycle Assessment for Renewable Methanol: Integrating Local Stakeholder Insights with PSILCA in openLCA

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Abstract:

Transition to renewable methanol is a key element in global decarbonization strategies, yet its social implications across the life cycle remain underexplored. This study advances the application of Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) to the H2Driven project (<https://h2driven.pt/en/>), focusing on the social and socio-economic impacts associated with renewable methanol production and distribution. This framework is grounded in the principles and requirements of ISO 14075:2024 [1], the UNEP Guidelines [2] and Methodological Sheets [3].

The assessment integrates primary data from stakeholder surveys—targeting workers and local community in Mangualde, Portugal—with secondary data from the Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment (PSILCA) database using openLCA. The study design follows the four iterative phases of S-LCA: goal and scope definition, social life cycle inventory (S-LCI), social life cycle impact assessment (S-LCIA) and interpretation. Stakeholder engagement and the selection of impact subcategories are aligned with international best practices, covering themes such as health and safety, fair salary, working hours, gender equality, local employment, access to resources, and community well-being.

Both reference scale and impact pathway approaches are applied, and reference scales are developed for each indicator, using performance reference points based on international conventions, local legislation, and sectoral best practices. The integration of local survey data reveals discrepancies between global risk profiles and local realities, highlighting the importance of contextualized S-LCA for robust decision-making.

Preliminary results indicate that renewable methanol offers significant environmental benefits but presents social challenges, particularly in upstream supply chains and local employment conditions. Key issues identified include variability in health and safety standards, gender equity gaps, and community expectations regarding economic opportunities. The study demonstrates

the feasibility and added-value of combining primary stakeholder data with established databases, in line with ISO 14075:2024 and UNEP recommendations.

This work contributes to the advancement of S-LCA methodology by operationalizing recent international standards and guidelines, and by providing actionable insights for policymakers and industry stakeholders seeking to ensure socially sustainable renewable methanol transitions. Future research will explore dynamic modelling approaches and incorporate social handprint metrics to capture positive contributions beyond risk mitigation.

This work was supported by H2Driven Green Agenda, project no. C644923817-00000037, financed by the Portuguese Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR).

References:

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Uncovering the Hidden Costs: Monetizing Environmental and Social Impacts in Fiberboard Production

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Abstract:

Sustainability assessments are vital during the research and development (R&D) of innovative and bio-based products to identify potential sustainability hotspots before industrialization, but the environmental, social and economic impact of a product can be hard to understand for non-experts. Until now most of the focus has been on assessing and communicating environmental sustainability impacts such as global warming potential (GWP), whereas social and economic sustainability have been largely neglected. For a holistic and comprehensive sustainability assessment, it is necessary to also assess a products social and economic sustainability. For this reason, this study monetizes the environmental and social impacts of a fiberboard with bio-based adhesive to create an integrated Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA). Monetizing the environmental and social impacts occurring in a cradle-to-gate system boundary of the fiberboard value chain can help in communicating the results to a broader audience. The products sustainability impacts are connected using the endpoint indicator “Damage to human health” and monetizing the environmental and social midpoint impacts associated with this indicator. The environmental impact of the fiberboard is calculated using EF 3.1 and the external costs are determined using the environmental prices defined by the European Commission. Environmental prices are also used for indicating the importance of the assessed impact categories. Social costs are context-dependent, making their measurement and assessment complex. The social impact will likely be monetized using methods such as the willingness to pay (WTP) for more sustainable products or estimated costs for social damage; the potential social risks are determined using the social hotspots database (SHDB) tool for social risk mapping.

The results are expected to show that the hotspots are associated with adhesive production, particularly with the conversion of fructose into hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) and the use of polylysine during adhesive production as a substitute for the fossil-based urea formaldehyde. Initial calculations have shown that polylysine is responsible for up to 97% of the environmental impact. The weighting of impact categories using the environmental prices revealed that Global Warming Potential (GWP), Particulate Matter Formation (PM) and Land Use (LU) are responsible

for the largest share of environmental impact. The highest midpoint social risks are associated with health and safety issues, in particular issues with toxic and hazardous substances.

Social sustainability assessment for new oil-water repellent biobased coatings applied to food and textile sectors

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AIMEN, O Porriño, Spain

Abstract:

The TORNADO project (Horizon Europe N° 101091944) aims to develop new organic and hybrid free-toxic water and oil-repellent coatings according to Safe- and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) criteria. The proposed novel coatings are PFAS-free.

One of the objectives of the project is to apply SSbD principles to the chemical and material design of innovative coatings. Within the framework of the project, a synthetic route based on functional biomonomers is developed and produced at laboratory and pilot scale. The aim is to obtain new bio-based waterborne organic and hybrid coatings, specifically designed for the packaging and textile sectors. Following that, these coatings are applied to various materials to replace conventional, non-biobased alternatives. For the packaging sector, a multilayer mayo sauce wrapper was selected, and for the textile sector, water-repellent garments were considered.

The use of the SSbD framework at an early stage of innovation is proving to be a useful decision support tool for selecting between different alternatives that are technically feasible in terms of safety, environmental (LCA) and economic sustainability (LCC). However, the social dimension is often neglected since its application is more challenging at low or medium technology readiness levels (TRL).

In the context of the TORNADO project, the efforts were focused on including the social dimension into the decision support process. To this end, a comprehensive social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) was conducted utilising different methodologies, specifically tailored to the different stages of the life cycle. For the manufacturing phase, a sector-country-specific assessment was performed, with support from the Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment (PSILCA) database, including all the upstream processes. For the use-phase, a site-specific assessment using the subcategory assessment methodology (SAM). For the end-of-life phase, a preliminary sector-country-specific qualitative assessment was performed.

In order to identify social hotspots, the results were analysed together and then aligned with the other dimensions of the SSbD framework.

How Sodium-Ion Batteries Lower Social Risks in the Material Extraction Phase? An S-LCA Perspective

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Abstract:

Sodium-ion battery (SiB) technology is becoming popular in academia and industry due to the use of non-critical raw materials. Though the economic and environmental impacts of the technology are promising, only limited knowledge has been achieved regarding the social aspects. The challenge in implementing social impact assessments mainly arises from methodological difficulties and data unavailability. Only a few articles are currently focused on social life cycle assessments; therefore, reflections on existing databases are not adequately developed. An attempt is made here to overcome these gaps and form a methodological framework to assess the social impact of sodium-ion batteries in comparison to benchmark Lithium-ion (LiB) storage devices. The focus is placed on the material extraction phase, where the highest social impacts usually occur due to poor working conditions. The functional unit of the study is the storage of 1 kWh of energy. The 55 indicators under the calculation method “social impact weighting” in the PSILCA v3 database were used for the assessment.

A clear reduction of social impacts can be seen in the case of SiBs in the extraction phase, mainly due to the non-availability of conflict minerals in the value chain. The highest impact for LiB is reported under Biomass consumption (access to natural resources for local communities) at 441.31 medium-risk hours (mrh), mainly linked to mining activities in Chile (Li), China (graphite), Russia, and Argentina. Increased mining activities in these areas put enormous pressure on land and biomass resources. In contrast, SiB can reduce this impact nearly fourfold due to the absence of Li and graphite in the cell chemistry. The second-highest impact in LiB is public sector corruption at 325 mrh, largely due to cathode and anode material supply chains, mainly related to Chile, the Republic of Congo, and China. This impact will be reduced by about threefold if SiB technology is adopted. On the other hand, a slight increase in Child labour, male, can be seen in the SiB value chain (67.86 mrh) compared to LiB (66.8 mrh), due to the higher fraction of steel sourced from India.

Reflections on the existing database and calculation methods were also made. Limited non-granular data in the database can distort real social impacts where country approximations are applied instead of sector-specific data. Moreover, the use of monetary terms to quantify social aspects remain major issues in SLCA. Studying complete supply-chain social impacts is highlighted as a future direction.

Social Life Cycle Assessment of the platinum value chain for the EU economy

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Abstract:

Platinum and other platinum group metals (PGMs) are pivotal materials for the EU economy, not only for the automotive industry, where they are a key material in autocatalyst, but will also play an important role in green energy transition, with the use and development of fuel cell and hydrogen (FCH) technologies. Within EU, one of the promising FCH technologies is PEM technology, which need PGM as the main catalyst.

The largest reserves of PGMs are in South Africa (88.9%), followed by Russia (7.8%), Zimbabwe (1.7%), the USA (1.2%), and Canada (0.4%). A bit different are the relative shares of platinum mined in 2023. South Africa mined 68.7% of the global platinum mined, Russia 13.2%, Zimbabwe 10.9%, Canada 3.0% and the USA 1.7%. Other countries together mined only 2.6% of platinum. The only European country with non-negligible platinum mining is Finland (0.5%).

The PGMs are on the 5th list of EU critical raw materials, emphasising the EU's dependence on imports of PGM, especially platinum. Furthermore, the platinum is highlighted in multiple studies as the main environmental and social hotspot in the production of PEM technologies. Therefore, a lot of effort is put into PGM recycling to avoid the EU's dependence on imports and to provide a more sustainable use of platinum within its lifecycle.

The presented study assesses the social impacts of different sources of platinum for the EU, the current value chain of platinum, platinum from Finland, and the recycling of platinum within the EU. The assessment follows the social life cycle assessment (LCA) methodology and SH2E guidelines for social LCA. The assessment is done in openLCA with the PSILCA database.

The supply chain of platinum is divided into four stages: extractive mining of platinum ore, production of platinum in unwrought or powder form, production of platinum in semi-manufactured form, and production of platinum catalysts. The recycling process of platinum is modelled based on the economic assessment of the platinum recycling process developed within the EU-funded project BEST4Hy. The recycling place is located in Germany and includes all the necessary chemicals and energy consumption needed for the recycling process.

The results indicate a significant benefit of recycling platinum, mainly due to the absence of mining, which contributes the most to the social impacts.

Sustainability Assessments of Plastics

LCA study on a carbon-negative PLA waste recycling method incorporating machine learning and transfer learning

Ouwen he

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Abstract:

An innovative and green PLA waste recycling method was developed. To know whether this technique has more environmental benefit compared with various chemical recycling solutions for handling end-of-life (EoL) post-consumer (PC) PLA waste. A perspective life cycle assessment of conceptual process design using the dry steam method to produce lactide from PLA waste was conducted, comparing it with incineration of PLA waste. To find the optimal reaction condition with less environmental impact, machine learning and transfer learning are used to search for several optimal reaction conditions for two different sets of experimental data.

PLA cup experimental data were used to model the process flow for dry steam treatment of discarded PLA cup sources using Aspen Plus, with detailed modeling and results outlined in the supporting material. Subsequently, the Aspen Plus modeling data were integrated into OpenLCA for further modeling. The results showed that the carbon emissions associated with the generation of lactide (LT) from PLA waste using dry steam were significantly lower (0.07 CO₂ eq/kg LT), even including the preprocessing phase (0.19 CO₂ eq/kg LT), than during traditional processes (1.02 CO₂ eq/kg LT).

Since lactic acid (LA) can achieve a higher yield than that of LT, we have also assessed the environmental performance of producing LT from LA derived from PLA cups. The carbon emissions associated with producing LA from PLA waste, including the pretreatment phase, are 0.7 kg CO₂ eq/kg LT. In contrast, the industrial-scale LT production from LA generates approximately 0.54 kg CO₂ eq/kg LT.^{12–14} The overall carbon emissions for producing LT from PLA waste via LA amount to 1.24 kg CO₂ eq/kg LT, which is higher than the dry steam method and traditional LT production methods.

These findings portend an environmentally friendly and effective strategy for recycling waste plastics and provide new insights into the depolymerization of polyesters.

STOPP - Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment of Reusable Plastic Food Packaging

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Abstract:

The EU Horizon funded project “STOPP” supports sustainable and circular use of plastic food packaging and decrease the amount of generated plastic food packaging waste. Building on the methodology developed during the EU project "PRIMUS" we combined environmental and social LCA, life cycle costing, circularity, plastic littering and system dynamics to create a holistic life cycle sustainability assessment for plastic food packaging, highlighting key aspects of sustainability that are widely overlooked in traditional environmental LCA.

In this presentation, we will demonstrate how this methodology can be applied to two re-use case studies covering different applications of reusable packaging across Europe.

Case Study 1: Comparison of single use with reusable food packaging in Swiss restaurants. This study highlights the ways in which consumer behaviour can affect the overall environmental impacts of reusable packaging.

Case Study 2: Comparison of single use with reusable pizza packaging in a Finnish context. Representing a more controlled system than the Swiss case study, this assessment investigates the ways in which decisions across the supply chain from cradle to grave (e.g. materiality, approach to use phase, end of life routes) can affect the overall impacts of reusable packaging.

The results of these studies will allow both suppliers and consumers to make informed decisions on the products they use and ultimately reduce impacts across the plastic food packaging value chain.

Life cycle assessment of a reusable shower packaging system

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Abstract:

In line with the circular economy, more and more alternatives are emerging in the field of packaging, such as reusable packaging. This type of packaging reduces the production of virgin plastics, as well as the amount of plastic waste produced.

In this context, the objective of this study is to assess the environmental impacts of reusable shower gel packaging through a life cycle assessment (LCA) and compare them with those of a standard disposable bottle.

The LCA was carried out in accordance with ISO 14040/14044 standards, from cradle to grave, from raw material extraction to waste treatment. The functional unit chosen was “containing one use of shower gel”; the two scenarios compared were a single-use one-liter bottle and a “Bag-In-Box” (BIB) system allowing consumers to refill a reusable one-liter bottle. The LCA modeling was carried out using OpenLCA software, and the environmental impacts were assessed using the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) method recommended by the European Commission; the single PEF score was also considered.

Inventory data was collected from industry stakeholders (manufacturers, distributors) and supplemented with data from the literature and the ecoinvent database. In order to take into account the use of recycled raw materials and end-of-life recycling, the circular footprint formula (CFF) was chosen. A sensitivity analysis was performed to compare this allocation rule with the cut-off method and the avoided impact method.

System Dynamics and LCSA

Measuring Circularity under Planetary Constraints: Circular Economy Indicators in a Holistic Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment of a Belgian Biogas Value Chain

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Abstract:

The circular economy is framed as a key strategy for achieving sustainability, yet many circularity agendas focus on technical loops and efficiency while neglecting questions of justice, sufficiency, and planetary boundaries. Reviews of circular economy indicators show that a large share of existing metrics capture the presence of circular economy activities, such as recycling, while neglecting associated resource extraction, emissions, and waste flows, thereby risking overstating environmental benefits. A sustainable circular economy must therefore be evaluated through indicators that link circular practices to both environmental pressures and questions of justice and sufficiency. Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) offers a starting point for integrating environmental, economic, and social dimensions, but existing applications often lack clear normative foundations and do not systematically reflect the tensions between circularity, justice, and absolute ecological constraints. The Holistic and Integrated Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (HILSCA) framework responds to this need by explicitly linking sustainability concepts, relations between society and nature, and life cycle thinking. Building on HILSCA, this study develops a structured review and selection of circular economy indicators, including material circularity, product circularity, and longevity metrics, and embeds them in an integrated assessment framework that links circular resource use to environmental pressures and social conditions. A Belgium-based biomethane value chain is used as a case study to examine how specific bioeconomy configurations affect circular resource use, environmental impacts, and social conditions in agricultural contexts. The results illustrate how combining HILSCA with selected circularity indicators can reveal trade-offs, rebound risks, and justice concerns that remain hidden in more technocratic visions of the circular economy. This article argues that indicator design and model choices are inseparable from broader debates on the aims and pathways of socio-ecological transformation.

Capturing Long-Term Trade-offs in Coffee Agribusiness: A System Dynamics - Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment of Kintamani Arabica Coffee

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Abstract:

The Arabica coffee landscape in Kintamani, Bali, Indonesia is a fragile ecosystem where cultural heritage and rural livelihoods are deeply intertwined. While the region benefits from Geographical Indication (GI) status and the stewardship of the traditional Subak Abian cooperatives, it faces mounting pressure from aggressive tourism, land conversion, and climate instability. Current sustainability assessments in the region are often static "snapshots," failing to capture how today's economic gains might compromise tomorrow's environmental resilience.

To address this, we developed an integrated framework combining Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) and System Dynamics (SD). We first used LCSA to quantify specific environmental, social, and economic impacts. We then embedded these indicators into a dynamic SD model to simulate the Kintamani coffee system over a multi-decadal horizon. Unlike previous models, this framework explicitly links "hard" variables like soil fertility and water availability with "soft" variables like Subak Abian institutional strength and tourism pressure.

Our simulations reveal a critical trade-off: uncontrolled agrotourism boosts short-term income but degrades the ecological foundation and weakens cooperative cohesion over time. However, the model also identifies leverage points. Interventions such as premium pricing for sustainability, strict agrotourism zoning, and organic waste valorization can reverse these trends. By turning static data into dynamic decision-making tools, this study offers a roadmap for policymakers to align modern agribusiness with the traditional philosophy of Tri Hita Karana.

Integrated LCSA with the HILCSA LCIA Method and Democratic Economic Planning as a System Dynamics Application in Agent Based Modelling

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Abstract:

Assessing the ecological, economic, and social sustainability of products and their production and consumption systems requires integrated frameworks for and of life cycle inventory (LCI) and life cycle impact assessment (LCIA). The soca database provides integrated social, environmental and economic data for system modelling and LCI. HILCSA (Holistic and Integrated Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment) is a corresponding LCIA method for soca and provides a one of its kind innovative and integrative assessment framework for comprehensive LCSA.

The HILCSA method is constantly applied in numerous case studies, revised and updated to the current requirements and newest soca database versions. The recent HILCSA v3 is available for licensing via nexus openLCA and integrates numerous qualitative and quantitative indicators by combining established LCIA methods into a single framework. Hereby, social, ecological, and economic dimensions of sustainability, as well as all 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), are addressed. The method provides a transdisciplinary and critical analysis of sustainability trade-offs, synergies, and hotspots in production and consumption systems.

HILCSA is not only applicable for relative but for absolute sustainability assessment as well as applying three Tokens (representative leading indicators: climate footprint, raw material footprint & labour footprint) to democratic economic planning (DEP) of societal metabolisms. How can we achieve a good life for all while staying within planetary boundaries? DEP is an economic tool which allows to identify viable pathways to determine which resources can be used, in what quantities, and through which economic, technological, and societal practices to sustainably satisfy societal needs.

We evaluate the systemic characteristics, potentials, and risks of this token system using an agent-based model for system dynamics. The model represents an average per-capita consumption basket in Germany, including its complex upstream production network. It simulates a dynamic societal metabolism in which the production structure adapts endogenously based on the decisions of individual consumers and producers. Early results

indicate that directing investment based on token-derived impact signals rather than monetary prices can reduce volatility and support more effective systemic transformation.

Can I Trust My Model? A Validation Approach for Sustainability Assessment with System Dynamics

Tomas Slany

GreenDelta, Berlin, Germany

Abstract:

Since System Dynamics (SD) models are constructed based on the modeller's conceptualization and understanding of reality, ensuring the validity of the obtained results is of essential importance. The reliability of an SD model is crucial not only for the modeller's confidence but also for enabling the decision-maker to confidently use the outputs generated by the model to inform their decisions. Hence, the validation of SD models emerges as an essential step for creating a useful model.

To fulfill this need, a validation framework for System Dynamics Sustainability Assessment (SDSA) was developed, addressing both the structural and behavioral aspects of the models. Furthermore, the framework was designed to allow for an agile testing of the model (considering the essentiality of each test and its time-efficiency), enabling the modeller to adjust the validation effort to the context of the assessment. To allow the applicability of this framework and the comparison of different models, a model-scoring approach based on the concept of saturation was developed.

This framework has subsequently been applied to the case of a System Dynamics model constructed for the sustainability assessment of the battery value chain in the EU HORIZON research project TREASoURcE. Specifically, the assessment examines the change in environmental impacts associated with the use of repurposed electric vehicle (EV) batteries for stationary energy storage. The SD model for this assessment was built in the software Stella, while openLCA was used to build the LCA model and link it to the SD model.

The results of this work will elucidate the main outcomes of the validation effort, highlighting the changes in the model that were informed by the validation tests, deepening the understanding of the model, and enabling a better interpretation of the results. The identified challenges related to validating models related to sustainability assessment (and other cases without corrective feedback loops) will be presented along with potential solutions and best practices. The results obtained from the assessment will be discussed in the context of the validation.

System dynamics and LCA in openLCA - 8 archetype models and questions.

What do we learn from them?

Andreas Citroth, Tomas Slany
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Abstract:

System dynamics is becoming an established approach for absolute sustainability questions and big picture LCA models. An often mentioned downside of system dynamics models is their nonlinear nature, where modeling decisions can largely affect system results and thus decisions taken when considering model insights. On the other side, system dynamics models are much better able to reflect changes over time, "memory" of a system e.g. for available resources, past impacts, and auxiliary variables. In this presentation, we provide 8 archetypes of decisions common in LCA models (including: does life time extension of a product make sense? Does recycling of a product make sense). These archetypes are able to provide general rules for these questions, which in turn can be used for a) early decision support in product and systems development, b) validation of LCA model results, c) making LCA modeling more focussed and more efficient, as the system dynamics models point to relations of system variables that are key for influencing the result; the LCA or also a more focussed system dynamics can then focus on these.

The presentation will show the archetypes and the conclusions they allow. It will also show the system dynamics models integrated in the LCA software openLCA and connected with LCA models, and discuss how this integration is able to truly advance state of the art in LCA modeling.

Applying system dynamics sustainability assessment (SDSA) to circular economy solutions in cities and regions: 3 different cases

Alexander Koch

GreenDelta, Berlin, Germany

Abstract:

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a standardised and broadly accepted methodology for a holistic assessment of sustainability over the life cycle. It has been proven useful since about 30 years, also due to their effective simplification of reality. When it comes to regional systems, consideration of developments over time and of links to a regional and broader economy are however often important as well. These are typically ignored in LCA.

In order to overcome such limitations, a sustainability assessment approach that combines system dynamics (SD) and LCA is presented. We call this system dynamics sustainability assessments (SDSA). This approach is especially addressing needs of a holistic sustainability assessment for regional systems, such as cities and regions. It has been developed and thoroughly tested in the EU-funded research project TREASoURcE. Regional cases were conducted for recycled plastics in the city of Gothenburg, 2nd life EV batteries in the greater region of Oslo, and the utilization of bio-based sidestreams in the region Pirkanmaa in Finland.

Overall, additional insights were given in all 3 cases by using SD and assessing CE solutions in the local context and market. It showed that it further allows 1) the exploration of how solutions may perform under different scenarios; 2) to identify indirect and unintended consequences such as rebound effects; 3) to consider multiple interest groups and associated trade-offs. Such an approach supports regional authorities in administering anticipatory, systems-aware governance, improving the likelihood that sustainability policies deliver their intended outcomes in practice.

Validating LCA Datasets

Data quality management in the MSDB database - what are good LCA datasets

Andreas Ciroth

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Abstract:

The MSDB database has been released meanwhile, and it is quite different from other LCA databases available - larger, more different unit processes, with parts obtained from various, also uncommon sources, including AI.

This presentation will focus on the data quality management of the database, also in comparison to other databases.

To this end, first, we will define what a "good LCA dataset" is, and then present the quality assessment framework for the database, which consists of a set of mandatory and of evaluation-based criteria for LCA datasets and life cycle chains, including structural integrity, natural science logic, representativeness, and triangulation support, and dedicated expert feedback and review, among others. The comparison to other databases will include unit process databases, system process databases, and IO databases.

Concluding, we will discuss ways forward towards an efficient and at the same time effective data quality management of very large LCA databases.

Validation of industrial data for LCI dataset

Lingjie Ji, Andreas Ciroth

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Abstract:

The goal of LCI data validation is to ensure datasets accurately reflect real-world production conditions. However, direct validation of industrial measured data—critical for LCI compilation—faces challenges: high on-site visit costs, limited monitoring infrastructure, potential data misreporting and production fluctuations. This presentation introduces a dual-dimensional validation framework tailored to these pain points, integrating internal (enterprise-specific data/logic) and external (industry-wide references). The presentation first outlines key LCI data categories: input material consumption, energy use and emission data. It then details some validation approaches: Internal validation includes—material balance (mass conservation + waste data + material loss accounting) paired with production records, validation of energy data via internal receipts/bills, and emissions linked to on-site process parameters. External validation validates industrial data with industry benchmarks to check its applicability.

Assessing Modelling Approaches in Chemical LCA Databases to Quantify Cumulative Uncertainty

Max Frederik Bringmann, Jonas Hoffmann
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Abstract:

Life cycle assessment (LCA) of chemicals is often limited by scarce primary data. For many substances, patents, reaction stoichiometry, and limited industrial data are the only sources available. Consequently, chemical synthesis processes in background LCA databases are frequently modelled with stoichiometric calculations supplemented by generic assumptions. While these assumptions enable broad coverage, they introduce uncertainty that often remains implicit. Because such processes are not explicitly labelled, identifying them requires additional steps that complicate LCA practice.

Using the ecoinvent database as a case study, we systematically assessed how prevalent generic modelling approaches are in major background databases. Facilitated by ecoinvent's rigorous documentation, particularly the descriptions of exchanges, we classified chemical production datasets according to the underlying data sources. Many datasets rely on generic information derived from environmental reporting of the Gendorf chemical park, which is explicitly referenced in the corresponding exchange descriptions. The presence or absence of these and other indicators allowed us to categorize datasets into four groups: (A) processes based on plant-level data, without references to Gendorf; (B) simulated or empirical datasets containing exchanges beyond simple stoichiometry; (C) partially empirical datasets drawing on sources other than Gendorf; and (D) generic datasets in which many exchanges use Gendorf data and stoichiometric modelling.

Across all chemical production datasets, we found that 55% fall into category A, 11% into B, 16% into C, and 18% into D. Our review also uncovered structural inconsistencies. Exchange descriptions are not harmonized, limiting machine readability. Some exchanges retain references to Gendorf-derived averages even when their numerical values do not match their data, suggesting generic values were used in co-production modelling. In addition, data quality indicators are applied inconsistently across categories, and the temporal coverage of generic sources varies between processes. Based on this four-category classification, we developed a framework to quantify cumulative uncertainty induced by multiple layers of generically

modelled synthesis steps, and we integrated this framework into the sustainability assessment of the SiToLub project's lubricant life-cycle model.

These findings demonstrate both the value of transparency and the challenges inherent in large-scale chemical modelling. As machine-learning approaches for automated chemical impact prediction become more common, understanding the structure and uncertainty of underlying data becomes increasingly important. Ecoinvent's detailed documentation enables such analyses and helps support discussion of uncertainty in generic data.

**When Regulations
Collide: Managing
Multiple
Sustainability
Frameworks in
Practice**

Beyond Double-Reporting: Building Trust in PCF Across Diverse Frameworks

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Abstract:

PCF calculation and reporting is becoming “mainstream”. More and more PCF standards are being created through industry associations such as Catena-X, Together For Sustainability (TFS) or Partnership for Carbon Transparency (PACT) but also regulations such as the Battery Regulation start to demand very specific reporting. Beyond the issue of double-reporting, these frameworks introduce a deeper complexity - how to ensure trust and comparability across diverse PCF values.

This session explores the practical implications of navigating this landscape. Drawing on TÜV SÜD's direct involvement in developing the Catena-X and TFS PCF Verification and Program Certification Frameworks, as well as our leadership in related workgroups, we will provide first-hand insights into verification approaches. This includes ISO-based audits, Catena-X & TFS verification schemes, and compliance as a Notified Body under the Battery Regulation. Attendees will gain a clear understanding of strategies to harmonize processes and maintain credibility in a fragmented regulatory environment.

Life cycle assessment in standards and legislation: navigating towards balanced degrees of freedom

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Abstract:

Life cycle assessment (LCA) practice is increasingly shaped by a dense web of standards and legislative acts, from ISO 14040/44 and ISO 14067 to application-specific EN standards, Environmental Footprint guidance, and product-focused regulations such as the EU Battery Regulation. While these frameworks aim to enhance consistency and robustness, they also create a complex landscape of partly overlapping and sometimes conflicting methodological requirements.

This contribution introduces a conceptual perspective on how strongly different normative references constrain key LCA modelling choices, such as end-of-life allocation, electricity modelling, and biogenic carbon. The concept of “degrees of freedom” is used to distinguish areas with tight prescription, areas with guided flexibility, and areas where practitioners retain wide methodological freedom. The pattern of constraints is illustrated across several domains, including packaging, wood-based products, and traction batteries, highlighting how different regulatory and standardisation contexts shape modelling practice.

The presentation will discuss how these varying degrees of freedom affect comparability, reproducibility, and interpretability of LCA results, particularly when studies are used for compliance, environmental claims, or third-party verification. Typical tension points are examined where standards and legislation leave critical issues underspecified, for example the interplay between recycling allocation approaches and recycled content claims, or between product-level footprints and internal corporate reporting frameworks.

Participants will learn i) how to read standards and regulations through the lens of degrees of freedom, ii) how to make normative choices explicit and transparent in their LCA documentation, and iii) how to critically reflect on when tighter prescription or greater methodological flexibility is appropriate, including the trade-offs for comparability, innovation and regulatory usefulness.

When your supply runs through China: Integrating China-specific LCI databases into European LCA, EPD & CBAM practice

Yuqing Zhand

HiQ Smart Data - HiQLCD, Shanghai, China

Abstract:

HiQLCD is China's high-resolution life cycle database designed to support global supply chains in achieving transparent, comparable, and decision-ready carbon footprint analysis. As European regulatory frameworks such as CBAM, EPD programs under EN 15804, and broader LCA-based reporting requirements increasingly rely on high-quality background data, the integration of representative Chinese life cycle inventory (LCI) data has become a critical challenge. Given China's approximately 30% share in global manufacturing and its major role in EU intermediate product imports, the absence of localized and up-to-date datasets can lead to distortions in supply chain assessments and regulatory reporting.

HiQLCD addresses this gap by providing high-resolution Chinese LCI datasets compatible with international methodological frameworks. The database supports cut-off, consequential, and EN 15804 system models and provides more than 20,000 datasets per system model. It covers over 1,000 products and 1,500 technologies across 8 major industry sectors and 26 sub-sectors, including energy, steel, chemicals, and electronics. All datasets are developed in compliance with ISO 14040/44, ISO 14067, and the ILCD Handbook to ensure methodological rigor and international comparability.

HiQLCD is fully compatible for import into major professional LCA tools, including openLCA, SimaPro, GaBi, and JimuLCA. It is listed on the UNEP-hosted GLAD platform and technically connected through the EU Life Cycle Data Network (LCDN) node, enabling interoperability with European LCA data infrastructures.

Use cases span industry leaders, academic research, government bodies, and industry associations, supporting applications such as PCF, EPD verification, and supply chain decarbonization. HiQLCD transforms data blind spots into precise, actionable insights for sustainable decision-making.

Multi-Agent Carbon Disclosure Evaluation for NEVs: Integrating Global Frameworks with Lifecycle and Supply Chain Metrics

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Abstract:

Achieving carbon neutrality has become a core pillar of the global strategy against climate change. Given that the transportation sector accounts for 25% of global carbon emissions, New Energy Vehicles (NEVs)—as a critical pathway for replacing traditional fossil fuel vehicles and driving deep decarbonization—play a decisive role in this strategy. However, the fragmentation of current disclosure standards and the lack of depth in traditional evaluation methods have compromised the transparency and credibility of carbon data. This limitation severely hinders data-driven climate governance and supply chain risk management. To address this, this study proposes a "Multi-Agent Cognitive Evaluation System" for carbon disclosure. This system integrates an evaluation standard specifically formulated for the NEV industry, which synthesizes global reporting frameworks (e.g., GRI, ISSB) with critical sector-specific metrics—such as full lifecycle battery carbon footprints and supply chain collaborative reduction—to establish a multi-dimensional and precise assessment system. By applying this system, the study conducts a detailed comparative analysis of ESG reports from representative global NEV enterprises. The proposed framework aims to transcend surface-level information and significantly enhance the transparency of carbon reporting, thereby empowering regulatory bodies and stakeholders to enforce effective supervision and risk identification. Ultimately, this research supports the NEV industry in mitigating supply chain risks and accelerating the transition toward carbon neutrality.

Poster

Advances in LCA Datasets

Rule-Based and ILCD-Conformant Validation of Automatically Generated LCA Datasets Using AI-Assisted JSON-LD Pipelines

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Abstract:

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is fundamentally dependent on large volumes of transparent, structured, and high-quality datasets, and as automation and artificial intelligence increasingly enable the rapid creation of unit process inventories, the challenge of ensuring methodological consistency and data reliability becomes more evident. Recent workflows capable of extracting information from heterogeneous documents—such as academic theses, reports, and open-data PDFs—and converting them into standards-ready JSON-LD files have accelerated dataset creation; however, the validation of these automatically generated datasets remains a critical step to guarantee compatibility with established LCA databases and analytical frameworks. This work presents a rule-based, ILCD-conformant validation framework designed to assess datasets produced through AI-assisted and automated extraction pipelines. The objective is to establish a scalable, transparent, and technically rigorous validation layer that ensures syntactic correctness, internal consistency, representativity, and methodological alignment before datasets are integrated into broader LCA repositories. The methodology includes four components: first, a syntactic and nomenclature validator that checks JSON-LD structure, nomenclature, units, and elementary flows according to ILCD requirements and openLCA rules, ensuring that datasets respect established naming systems and data models. Second, automated balance-of-mass and energy routines evaluate coherence between input and output flows, calculating percentage deviations and assigning scores on a scale from 1 to 5, where, for example, an 85% imbalance yields a score of around 4.25. Third, a pedigree-based scoring system evaluates technological, geographical, and temporal representativity as well as completeness and uncertainty, assigning weighted ILCD-based factors that generate an aggregated Data Quality Rating (DQR) with qualitative interpretation. Finally, a supervised practitioner review captures anomalies and contextual considerations that exceed the detection capacity of automated rules, maintaining methodological robustness and traceability. Preliminary tests using datasets automatically generated from Mexican academic sources—national LCA projects, scientific articles, and theses—show that the use of localized data introduces substantial variability relative to international datasets, reinforcing the need for systematic validation. Early results reveal documentation gaps, moderate temporal misalignment, and

occasional balance inconsistencies, all effectively detected and quantified through the proposed scoring framework. The rule-based ILCD-aligned validation module thus offers a scalable and transparent approach to strengthening the credibility and usability of AI-generated LCA datasets. Ongoing development focuses on refining scoring algorithms, expanding rule-based coverage, and integrating semi-automated expert feedback to further enhance dataset reliability and support the creation of robust LCA databases.

Agriculture & Bioeconomy

Integrating MFA, openLCA, and ESG/S-LCA for Circular Bioeconomy Transitions: A Case Study of Organic Waste-to-Compost Systems for Urban Agriculture

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Abstract:

The transition to a circular bioeconomy increasingly demands integrated analytical frameworks capable of addressing the environmental, social, and governance dimensions of agricultural resource systems. This study presents a combined Material Flow Analysis (MFA), environmental Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) using openLCA, and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) enriched with ESG indicators to evaluate urban organic waste-to-compost pathways. The analysis focuses on food waste, green waste, and mixed organic residues commonly generated in urban households, examining their conversion into high-quality compost for use in urban farming and aquaponic production.

MFA quantified mass flows, nutrient recovery efficiencies, and conversion dynamics across the composting chain, enabling the identification of critical hotspots for system improvement. Environmental impacts were modelled in openLCA using the EF 3.1 and ReCiPe methods, with particular attention to climate change, eutrophication, resource depletion, and human toxicity. The S-LCA/ESG assessment examined labour conditions, governance practices, community benefits, and alignment with contemporary sustainability reporting frameworks relevant to the bioeconomy.

Findings indicate that optimised composting reduces greenhouse gas emissions by 25–40 per cent relative to landfilling while significantly enhancing nutrient circularity. The social and governance evaluations highlight strengthened community engagement, potential for job creation, and improved adherence to urban sustainability priorities. The integrated MFA–openLCA–ESG framework thus provides a robust decision-support tool for policymakers, municipal agencies, and urban agriculture practitioners seeking to expand circular bioeconomy initiatives. The study offers a replicable model for advancing resilient and resource-efficient urban agricultural systems in rapidly growing cities.

Keywords: Circular Bioeconomy; Life Cycle Assessment (LCA); Material Flow Analysis (MFA); Organic Waste Valorisation; Urban Agriculture Sustainability

Life cycle assessment and techno-economic analysis for 1G ethanol production plant upgrading

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Abstract:

Bioethanol, as a green energy source, holds great promise in replacing fossil fuels. Currently, most bioethanol is produced from food crops using first-generation (1G) technologies, which face challenges like food vs. fuel competition and limited scalability. Second-generation (2G) bioethanol uses lignocellulosic biomass, which is abundant, low-cost, and emits up to 85% fewer greenhouse gases. This study explores the environmental effects of incorporating 2G processes into a 1G ethanol production plant. This research examines the feasibility of integrating agricultural waste as alternative feedstocks (rice straw and wheat straw) into the existing 1G ethanol production system, employing the concept of phased implementation—a strategic approach that identifies the long-term potential of technology pathways as they progress toward commercial viability. This integration from 1G to 2G ethanol production would leverage existing infrastructure such as pretreatment, fermentation, distillation, and wastewater treatment, thereby reducing capital expenditure and enhancing overall efficiency. This proposed strategy reduces reliance on food resources, increases feedstock flexibility, supports a circular bioeconomy, and enhances ethanol plant resilience to market fluctuations. The proposed strategy focuses on reducing reliance on food-based feedstocks while increasing stability and flexibility by adopting alternative sources like wood and agricultural waste. This approach would aid ethanol plants in better handling market fluctuations and improving revenue over time; furthermore, it could improve the feedstock flexibility and supply chain robustness. 1G ethanol production sustainability and economic competitiveness of 1G bioethanol production by upgrading feedstock from food-based feedstocks to agricultural waste. This study provides a pathway to transform 1G bioethanol plants into more economically competitive and environmentally sustainable biorefineries.

LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT WITH NUTRITIONAL APPROACH: A CASE STUDY OF A CIRCULAR GLUTEN-FREE BREAD

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Abstract:

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is used to evaluate the environmental impacts of food products, usually expressed per mass of product. However, this approach does not consider nutritional quality, relevant when comparing foods of different compositions. This study investigates gluten-free bread enriched with apple pomace flour (APF), a by-product of cider production, using both conventional LCA and nutritional LCA (nLCA). The assessment was carried out in OpenLCA software using the Ecoinvent and Agribalyse databases and experimental data, following the Environmental Footprint 3.1 methodology and a cradle-to-gate approach. The functional unit for LCA was 1kg of bread produced at laboratory scale and for nLCA it was the Spanish Nutrient Rich Food 9.2 Index, which integrates key nutrients per 100g of product. Breads with 0%, 6% and 10% APF were evaluated, representing realistic proportions from previous studies. In the formulations with APF each gram of APF replaced one gram of a flour mix (rice: buckwheat: corn= 0.51:0.31:0.18), reducing the upstream impacts associated with these flours.

In the conventional LCA, adding 10% APF increased ionizing radiation, an energy-related category, from 0.21 to 0.24 kBq U-235 eq/kg (relative to the control). This increase was related to the drying step required for APF production, highlighting that by-product processing may represent a critical stage. However, most categories improved with 10% compared to 0%: global warming potential reduced from 0.74 to 0.64 kg eq CO₂/kg, land use by 19.3% and water use by 31.16%. These reductions reflect the partial replacement of cereal-based flours. When environmental impacts were expressed per unit of nutritional quality, APF containing breads showed lower impacts than the control. Differences were more pronounced using the

nutritional index due to the nutritional density of APF; breads with 6% and 10% APF achieved nutritional scores of 53.6 and 68.4, respectively, compared to 29.9 for the control. For example, with 10% of APF, global warming potential decreased by 62%, land use 64.7% and fossil resource demand by 55.3%, relative to the control.

This integrated approach shows that combining nutritional and environmental assessment provides a more comprehensive evaluation of food products. Minimally processed by-products can improve nutritional quality while maintaining or reducing environmental impacts, which supports the development of sustainable and nutritious gluten-free breads. The nLCA could support digital applications in the food sector that communicate both nutritional quality and environmental impacts to consumers, allowing meaningful comparison between products.

Buildings: LCAs and climate mitigation strategies

Are Construction Materials a Net Carbon Emitter or Sink? A Conservative LCA-Based Evaluation with Conservation of Mass

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Abstract:

The potential of construction materials to absorb carbon dioxide (CO₂) has gained considerable attention as a climate-mitigation strategy. Materials containing reactive oxides such as CaO, MgO or K₂O can bind CO₂ via carbonation, prompting increasing interest in “carbon-negative” construction products. However, evaluating materials solely based on their CO₂-uptake capacity, while neglecting the emissions associated with creating the reactive oxides, can lead to misleading conclusions.

Therefore, the focus of this study is to holistically evaluate the true sequestration potential of selected organic-inorganic materials through conservation-of-mass reasoning (maximum theoretical CO₂ uptake was determined via stoichiometry) and cradle-to-gate life cycle assessment (LCA) using the “IPCC 2021” Life Cycle Impact Assessment method implemented in OpenLCA 2.5. A deliberately conservative allocation approach is applied: whenever multiple products emerge from the same process, the full carbon burden is attributed to the potential sequestration material. Data are gathered through experimental evaluation of the materials, literature and Ecoinvent v3.11 database.

The evaluated materials were wood and wood-derived fly ash (FA) from thermal power plants, and alkali-activated material (AAM) synthesised from FA:

1. In the case of wood-based systems, combustion is performed primarily for energy generation, during which biogenic carbon, captured during tree growth, is converted back into CO₂ while exposing the inorganic oxides (CaO, MgO, K₂O) to air for post-combustion carbonation. Two carbon-accounting scenarios were examined: (a) systematic reforestation (one tree replanted for every tree harvested and allowed to grow for at least an equivalent period; and the calculated number of trees required to achieve net-zero), and (b) absence of reforestation, reflecting accelerated human-induced CO₂ release.
2. FA is heavily investigated as a sole precursor for AAM, a potential alternative to conventional cements. However, the dominant source of emissions in AAM arises from alkali activators. A range of different alkalis and dosages is therefore modelled to identify FA-to-alkali mass ratios

at which the system could theoretically achieve net-negative performance, while also respecting practical limits (efflorescence and compromised mechanical properties at high alkali contents). In the modelling, the optimal molar ratio of amorphous silica to aluminium to alkali (earth) elements was taken as 1.9 to 1 to 1 (0.5) [1], respectively, i.e., values that give the highest mechanical performance and avoid efflorescence.

The results show that net-negative performance in evaluated systems is possible when reforestation is practised, as well as that a combined stoichiometry-LCA approach is essential to reliably identify materials with genuine climate-beneficial sequestration potential.

Energy Systems

LCA of precious metal recycling of PEM electrolysis cells using the material criticality indicator of the openLCA criticality package

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Abstract:

The utilization of hydrogen across various sectors is a key technology for achieving a sustainable energy future. Among the existing electrolysis cell technologies, proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolysis offers high efficiency and pure hydrogen results. However, especially their components porous transport layer (PTL) and bipolar plates (BPP) contain precious metals, that significantly increase both the economic and environmental costs of the technology. To mitigate these impacts, circular strategies for those components and metals are essential. Approaches as such have the potential to enhance the economic viability and environmental sustainability of PEM electrolysis and thus support their broader adoption for efficient and pure hydrogen production.

Therefore, this study analyses the environmental impacts of PEM electrolysis cells through LCA, with a focus on different 2nd life strategies of the two critical components PTL and BPP. Different literature benchmarks are altered and compared by various end of life and recycling scenarios to data derived from disassembly of an out-of-service stack.

For the assessment, the study uses the circularity package for openLCA, which is based on the database ecoinvent 3.10 and contains additional information for circularity and material criticality.

Besides the well-known LCA impact categories, a special focus is set on the criticality indicator provided within the used database package. Using this indicator, the study emphasizes the criticality and thus also the importance for a responsible usage of the precious metals within the PTL and BPP, and highlights the advantages of circular 2nd life applications for PEM components.

Thus, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of environmental and material implications associated with PEM electrolysis components. With its findings, it contributes to the development of more sustainable design and end-of-life strategies for PEM technologies. By providing insights that help researchers and policymakers develop frameworks supporting

responsible material usage in the hydrogen sector, this study further strengthens the foundation for a circular hydrogen economy.

Life Cycle Assessment of a Tank Thermal Energy Storage (TTES) Integrated into a District Heating Network

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Abstract:

Thermal energy storage systems (TES) are increasingly recognized as a key technology for enabling low-carbon district heating. By decoupling heat generation from demand, TES enhance system flexibility and stability. Despite their growing importance, the life-cycle environmental impacts of TES, particularly associated with operational charging and discharging remain underexplored. This study investigates the thermal tank energy storage (TTES), with 1350 MWh capacity, to evaluate its environmental performance using a life cycle assessment framework. The tank is situated in the district heating network Linz, an industrial city in Austria. The objective is to compare the current operation with TTES against a hypothetical scenario without TTES.

The LCA was implemented in openLCA using the ecoinvent 3.11 cut-off database. The reference period is a one-year heat supply. The functional unit is 1 MWh of thermal energy delivered to the network, either via the storage or supplied directly without it. A 30-year operational lifetime is assumed. Environmental impacts were calculated using the ReCiPe (2016) midpoint indicators with a hierarchic perspective. Heat generation with and without storage was modeled using a tool based on the Heat Merit Order approach, providing differences per generation unit for the operation with and without TTES. Allocation of environmental burdens between heat and electricity was examined through multiple methods. This includes defined processes, exergy-based approaches, the Finnish method, and system expansion with electricity substitution.

Results indicate that, due to the large cumulative energy throughput (~3 TWh), the construction-related impacts are minor, representing below 1% of total CO₂-equivalents, across all scenarios. Using defined processes and exergy allocation, TTES operation leads to annual savings of 2,279 t and 2,805 t CO₂-equivalents, respectively. In contrast, the Finnish method indicates negative impacts for the TTES, as heat generation of combined heat and power plants is assessed as more carbon-intensive than peak boiler heat. Substituting with coal-based electricity suggests reduced CO₂-equivalents with and without TTES, while conventional

natural gas-based substitution nearly halves emissions, resulting in 89.4 kg CO₂-eq/MWh with TTES and 122.0 kg CO₂-eq/MWh without. Substitution with wind power also indicates negative impacts for operation with TTES, as it indicates minimal avoided carbon. These findings highlight that TTES-related construction emissions are rapidly offset when charged with low-carbon heat. This effect scales with the cycle number. Furthermore, the study underscores the influence of allocation methodology on LCA outcomes, emphasizing the need for transparency in evaluating TES in district heating networks.

Analysis of the Contribution of Hydrogen Energy Transition in Korea's Energy-Intensive Industries

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Abstract:

In recent years, hydrogen energy has gained attention as a key solution for decarbonizing the industrial sector. For Korea in particular, the need for a large scale hydrogen utilization strategy has become increasingly important due to the country's carbon intensive industrial structure, including steel, petrochemicals, and cement. To support national energy policy, research is required to comprehensively assess the greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential that may arise when substituting final energy consumption in the industrial sector with hydrogen. Reflecting these national circumstances, this study calculated GHG emissions per kilogram of gray, blue, green, and imported hydrogen based on Korea's hydrogen production and import targets. It also conducted a supply demand analysis using linear regression and evaluated emissions under scenarios in which hydrogen replaces industrial energy demand.

The comparison between Korea's hydrogen supply targets and a scenario in which 10% of current energy demand in energy intensive industries is converted to hydrogen indicates a significant supply demand mismatch in the near term. The results show a hydrogen shortfall of approximately 2.86 million tons in 2020 and about 80,000 tons in 2030. However, by 2050, a substantial surplus of around 22.31 million tons emerges. Analysis of GHG emission changes following energy substitution further demonstrates that hydrogen adoption can reduce emissions by 36% in 2020, 70% in 2030, and 81% in 2050 compared with fossil fuels. The larger reductions in 2030 and 2050 are primarily attributable to the increasing share of green and imported hydrogen, which significantly amplifies the mitigation effect.

Additionally, this study evaluated the GHG reduction impact of converting 10% of Korea's energy intensive industries to hydrogen in the baseline year of 2023, the 2030 Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) target year, and the 2050 carbon neutral target year. The analysis found that hydrogen conversion in 2023 could generate a reduction effect equivalent to about 5% of the nation's total GHG reduction needs. This outcome corresponds to 399% of the 2030 hydrogen sector reduction target and 372% of the 2050 carbon neutral scenario (Hydrogen Reduction Plan B).

In summary, the study confirms that substantial GHG reductions in the industrial sector are achievable when policy foundations expanding the hydrogen supply chain, establishing power-hydrogen linkage infrastructure, and strengthening international cooperation for hydrogen imports are firmly in place.

Assessment of Electrolytic Hydrogen Carbon Intensity under Changing Power Mix and Nuclear-Based Supply Scenarios in Korea

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Abstract:

As many countries declare carbon neutrality, interest in hydrogen as an energy carrier with no direct CO₂ emissions has been growing. Korea also regards hydrogen as a key future energy source and is preparing a Clean Hydrogen Certification Scheme that will provide incentives to producers whose hydrogen meets a specified greenhouse gas (GHG) emission threshold. This study aims to quantify the life-cycle carbon intensity of green hydrogen produced via water electrolysis in Korea, considering the national clean hydrogen certification criteria, and to analyse how changes in the power generation mix and the use of nuclear power as a dedicated electricity source affect that intensity.

Based on the latest national power supply–demand plan, grid emission factors are derived for both the current Korean power mix and the projected 2030 power mix. Using these emission factors, the GHG emissions per unit of hydrogen (kg CO₂eq/kg H₂) are calculated for three scenarios: (1) electrolysis using the current grid mix, (2) electrolysis using the projected 2030 grid mix, and (3) electrolysis supplied exclusively by nuclear power through dedicated nuclear-powered electrolyser facilities. The resulting carbon intensities are then compared with the Korean Clean Hydrogen Certification threshold to evaluate compliance in each scenario. Finally, the study discusses policy implications for power mix planning and nuclear utilisation strategies to expand the supply of certified clean hydrogen in Korea.

Regionalized Life Cycle and Circularity Assessment of NMC Cathode Production: Global, Canadian, and Recycling Scenarios

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Abstract:

The decarbonisation of the transport sector has led to the transition away from internal combustion engines and towards the electrification of road transportation. Electric vehicles rely on lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) that commonly serve 5–8 years before declining below ~80% capacity and exiting traction service. The continuous growth of EV sales therefore implies a rising stream of end-of-life (EoL) batteries and an urgent need for effective LIB waste management. Recycling presents an opportunity to recover critical materials (Ni, Co, Mn, and Li), reducing dependence on virgin extraction and potentially lowering environmental burdens, while supporting an increasingly domestic and circular supply chain.

Canada possesses domestic reserves of key LIB minerals, with active mining operations across multiple provinces. Québec contributes to this resource potential with large hard-rock spodumene deposits and existing nickel and cobalt production. With a predominantly renewable grid (~94% hydropower), Québec is well positioned for environmentally favorable battery-materials production across the value chain; however, the environmental implications of housing the full supply chain for cathodes in Canada have yet to be investigated.

We develop a comparative life cycle assessment (LCA) of three pathways for producing nickel–manganese–cobalt (NMC) battery cathode: (1) a global virgin production scenario representing current market-average supply chains (GLO); (2) a Canadian virgin production scenario constructed through geospatial optimization of emerging Canadian mining, refining, and midstream facilities; and (3) a hydrometallurgical recycling scenario situated entirely within the Canadian context. All scenarios use a functional unit of 1 kg of NMC-based cathode active material. Modelling is conducted in openLCA using Ecoinvent v3.10, literature-derived LCIs, and the Impact World+ LCIA method. Circularity indicators are additionally quantified using the openLCA Circularity Package to complement environmental results.

The analysis evaluates environmental impacts across multiple categories and incorporates avoided-burden credits to quantify the displacement of virgin materials through recycling. Geospatial mapping of facility locations, combined with provincial electricity-grid intensities, supports the construction of the Canada-specific supply chain. Results compare the two virgin scenarios to determine how regionalized, Canada-specific supply chains reshape environmental hotspots relative to global averages. Additional comparisons between each virgin production scenario and Canadian hydrometallurgical recycling (accounting for avoided burdens) highlight the potential environmental benefits and trade-offs associated with integrating recycled materials into Canadian battery manufacturing.

Overall, results demonstrate how regionalization, circularity potential, and recycling integration influence the environmental performance of emerging North American battery production systems and provides insights for designing low-impact, circular Canadian LIB supply chains.

openLCA Tools and Integration: Lessons Learned and Shared Experiences

Integrating the Sustainable Process Index into OpenLCA: Advancing Ecological Footprint Assessment in Life Cycle Assessment

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Abstract:

The Sustainable Process Index (SPI) is an ecological footprint method that quantifies environmental impacts through the land area required to offset emissions and regenerate natural resources. Unlike other impact assessment methods, the SPI consolidates resource use and emissions to air, water, and soil into a single metric expressed in square meters per year [m².a/unit], eliminating the need for normalization and weighting.

Developed at Graz University of Technology in the 1990s, SPI is currently applied via the browser-based tool SPIONWeb.eco to evaluate ecological footprints, greenhouse gas potential, and CO₂ emissions of products, services, and organizations. These assessments support sustainable business strategies and product development by providing verifiable ecological impact data.

To ensure continued scientific robustness and efficiency of use, the SPI method is being modernized and integrated into the open-source LCA software OpenLCA. This integration will allow LCA practitioners to apply the SPI within contemporary LCA modeling frameworks and to connect the method to commonly used databases.

Unlike traditional impact assessment methods that aggregate all elementary flows, SPI employs the concept of “key emission areas,” considering only the largest direct emission impact per process. This approach reflects the ecological principle that one square meter of area can absorb multiple substances simultaneously, thus only counting the biggest area for direct emissions. The key emission area is added to the footprint resulting from other inputs (product flows and resource use). This requires dedicated programming beyond standard characterization factor assignments. Additionally, the characterization factors for individual substances will be updated and expanded during implementation.

The consortiums (STRATECO, akaryon and acib) objective is to develop a prototype implementation of SPI within an upstream fork of OpenLCA, incorporating its distinctive calculation logic. Following internal testing and cross-platform adaptation, we aim to make the

open-source SPI module publicly available. This advancement will bridge the gap between ecological footprint methodologies and mainstream LCA tools, offering practitioners a scientifically sound and efficient approach to assess the total area for embedding of human activities sustainably into the ecosphere.

Mapping Material Flows for Automated Life Cycle Assessment

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Abstract:

Automating Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) requires establishing reliable connections between internal material descriptions and the flow structures used in Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) databases. In a manufacturing context, this mapping step represents one of the most persistent obstacles to scaling LCA across large and heterogeneous product portfolios. Data found in Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems are often inconsistent, multilingual, and shaped by local conventions, whereas LCI databases follow strict domain-specific naming schemes. As a result, a single method cannot manage the inconsistencies across datasets, making a multi-layered mapping approach necessary for automation.

The growing demand for product-level environmental data from customers and supply-chain partners has increased the pressure on manufacturers to produce LCA-based information consistently and at scale. Organizations with large product portfolios and complex supply chains face significant practical constraints when environmental modeling relies on the manual interpretation of material data. Automation is therefore central to enabling LCA adoption at scale and requires both conceptual clarity and robust technical interfaces between enterprise datasets and LCA modeling tools.

We present a conceptual four-stage pipeline for automated flow mapping that organizes the mapping into different layers. Each stage produces a confidence score for every flow, enabling mappings above the predefined threshold to be accepted automatically while ambiguous cases move on through successive layers.

The first stage in the pipeline is identifier-based matching, which uses unique references such as CAS numbers when these are present in the enterprise data. This step resolves a subset of flows with high certainty, as identifiers provide a direct link to specific flows. If unique identifiers are not available, a second stage applies algorithmic string-to-string similarity to generate candidate mappings based on character-distance matching between enterprise descriptions and LCI flow names. A third stage applies an LLM-based comparison that incorporates contextual information from the material descriptions, enabling assessment of candidates that string-based methods cannot reliably map. Only flows unresolved at this point continue to a final stage of manual confirmation.

The pipeline integrates enterprise material data with openLCA by using the olca-ipc package to transfer mapped flows directly into the modeling environment. This creates a structured interface between internal data systems and openLCA, allowing downstream LCA modeling to proceed without manual re-entry of material flows and maintaining traceability over how each mapping decision was produced.

Consistent LCA Modelling for Packaging and Related Challenges

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Abstract:

This article highlights key methodological challenges in developing an LCA tool for packaging as integrated in the Packaging Cockpit, a digital platform. The methodology aims to assess environmental impacts of different packaging formats in a comparable and scientifically sound manner, despite limited data while considering current regulatory requirements. The methodology is based on the European Commission's Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) method, including EF 3.1 and the Circular Footprint Formula (CFF), enabling assessment of 16 impact categories. Secondary data from ecoinvent is modified and prepared in openLCA. The implementation of CFF poses several key challenges: it requires 100% virgin material datasets to correctly allocate burdens and credits at the end-of-life (EoL). As such datasets are only partially available in ecoinvent, affected material datasets are extrapolated and harmonised to avoid double-counting.

Further, the end-of-life is central to any packaging LCA. The Packaging Cockpit, therefore, combines the LCA with a recyclability assessment aligned with current regulations, ensuring realistic shares of recycling, energy recovery and landfill. A key challenge lies in different system boundaries: available recycling rates are not always compatible with ecoinvent and combining them carries the risk of distortions such as double counting of sorting losses. To solve this issue, an extended EoL-logic, for example, tracks plastics all the way to pelletised recyclate and clearly separates losses covered by ecoinvent from those requiring additional modelling, enabling consistent allocation in line with CFF, available recycling rates and ecoinvent.

Regionalisation represents a further challenge, as many packaging-relevant ecoinvent datasets are not sufficiently country-specific. To approximate regional differences, datasets are adjusted mainly through national electricity mixes. While simplified, this approach pragmatically improves representativeness.

Additionally, material-specific inconsistencies are identified and corrected, such as geographically inconsistent water flows in plastics. Such deviations have a considerable impact on individual impact categories and require targeted data cleaning and plausibility checks.

Overall, the development of a robust packaging LCA tool depends on the careful harmonisation of data sources, methodological requirements and regulatory frameworks. The analysis demonstrates that the correct application of the CFF and realistic modelling of recycling pathways are essential to prevent distortions and ensure transparent allocation of burdens and credits. At the same time, limited regionalisation and dataset inconsistencies underline the need for systematic data preparation and continuous validation. Only a rigorously harmonised and transparently documented methodology can ensure reliable and decision-relevant LCA results for packaging.

Sandbox Session

From Bauxite to Aluminium: A Life Cycle Assessment of Key Processing Stages

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Abstract:

Aluminium is a globally strategic material for the green transition. Its production is characterized by high energy demand, resource intensity, and complex supply chains. Properties, such as lightweight and high recyclability, give aluminium a vital role in low-carbon mobility, renewable energy technologies, infrastructure, and electrification. This analysis presents a cradle-to-gate Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of primary aluminium production in two regions—China and the European Union with 27 member states plus the European Free Trade Association (EU27+EFTA). The assessment covers primary aluminium production key processes: bauxite mining and beneficiation, alumina refining via Bayer Process, calcination, aluminium smelting through Hall–Héroult Process, and primary aluminium ingot production. The goal is to assess and quantify environmental impacts across key processing stages and to examine implications for aluminium’s role as a critical material in the emerging low-carbon economy. Inventory data are collected from ecoinvent 3.12 and International Aluminium Institute (IAI) reports.

To estimate the relevance of environmental impacts and assess methodological sharpness, the study applies two widely used LCA methods—CML v4.8 2016 and ReCiPe 2016 v1.03 midpoint (H). Comparing these methods reveals variations in characterization models and supports comprehensive interpretation of environmental hotspots in aluminium processing stages. Preliminary results show that aluminium smelting—the Hall–Héroult Process—is main contributor to cradle-to-gate impact. It requires high energy input to maintain smelter temperatures of 960–980 °C: 179 MJ and 74 MJ (4.16 kg oil-Eq and 1.73 kg oil-Eq) for 1kg liquid aluminium, produced in China and EU27+EFTA, respectively. Energy consumption directly affects the climate change indicator, with values of 20.5 and 7.9 kg CO₂-Eq depending on the production geography. The assessment shows up to a threefold difference in energy demand and climate change between regions. Although bauxite mining contributes less to energy demand and climate change, it strongly affects metal and mineral resource depletion.

Regional electricity mixes affect environmental implications, notably when comparing aluminium produced in China, which depends heavily on coal, with aluminium production in

EU27+EFTA, where electricity generation incorporates both fossil fuels and renewables. Given the importance of aluminium for green technologies, understanding environmental burdens is vital for estimating sustainability trade-offs related to decarbonization strategies. This study provides a comprehensive environmental profile of primary aluminium production, highlighting smelting as the most critical stage, and the need for transnational strategies to balance growing aluminium demand with responsible resource governance.

Development of a Life Cycle Assessment Framework for Early-Stage Ship Design

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Abstract:

The continuously changing regulatory frameworks such as International Maritime Organization (IMO)'s greenhouse gas (GHG) Strategy and FuelEU Maritime are pushing the maritime industry towards net-zero GHG emissions. To achieve net-zero emissions in the shipping sector, the sustainability assessments should be part of the early-phase concept design so the insights from it can be fed back into the design process for marine vessels which often have long operational life. However, it is challenging to perform forward-looking life cycle assessment (LCA) in the early-phase concept design due to limited data, uncertain system boundaries, and immature technologies. This work therefore developed a framework for performing Prospective Life Cycle Assessment (pLCA) using openLCA, and Premise tool in the concept design phase of ships. The framework reduces the methodological and practical challenges through literature synthesis, development of a guideline, and case study validation.

The proposed pLCA framework utilizes flexibility, transparency, modularity, and iterative use to allow concept phase assessment across varying data maturity and Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs). The pLCA framework was implemented on the Avatar 110 gross tonnage (GT) cruise ship concept developed at Meyer Turku. The study analyzed several stages such as construction, operations, and End-of-Life (EOL) with two comparative fuel pathways (Marine Gas Oil (MGO) vs Methanol (MeOH) with MGO as pilot fuel) over the 35-year lifetime of the vessel (2030–2064).

The case study results show that the MeOH pathway reduced the fuel's well-to-wake (WTW) Global Warming Potential (GWP) by 25% as compared to the MGO baseline due to lower tank-to-wake (TTW) emissions. However, these benefits are offset by increased upstream well-to-tank (WTT) emissions for MeOH pathway making it critical to decarbonize upstream production pathways. The importance of holistic system-level assessments beyond operational emissions was realized because of key trade-offs identified from other midpoint indicators such as acidification and water consumption.

This work demonstrates a novel ship-level implementation of an Integrated Assessment Model (IAM)-aligned, parameterized pLCA framework, offering a methodological foundation for early integration of environmental assessment into ship concept design. Future research should focus on establishing integrated data flows between design teams and LCA tools, reducing reliance on rough estimates and fragmented, inconsistent ship-design data. Strengthening automation between ship design software, material databases, and LCA tools is essential for timely, transparent, and accurate assessments. Furthermore, Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and energy systems model can be integrated with LCA to enable real-time sustainability and economic product performance feedback loops.

Social LCA Case Studies

Social Risk Life Cycle Assessment of Emergent Bio-bleaching Process for Wearable Electronic Textile

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Abstract:

Electronic textiles (e-textiles) are advanced fabrics that seamlessly integrate functionalities such as sensors, conductive pathways, and energy storage directly into their structure. While they offer significant opportunities for innovation, achieving holistic sustainability requires a robust evaluation of social dimensions alongside traditional environmental and economic factors. Discussing social subcategories is uniquely critical for e-textiles, as they merge the complex labor challenges of the garment industry with the hazardous manufacturing and sourcing risks of the electronics sector. For such emerging technologies, defining relevant social subcategories is often hindered by limited literature, yet this selection is vital as it fundamentally dictates the accuracy of Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) results.

Conducted within the European Horizon Project UPWEARS (ID 101130741), this study proposes a framework for mapping the essential steps of an e-textile S-LCA, focusing specifically on stakeholder-driven subcategory selection. While the UNEP guidelines generally identify six stakeholder groups, this research prioritizes the three most directly impacted by the UPWEARS project: workers, consumers, and local communities.

Using a survey-based approach, these stakeholders ranked subcategories from the UNEP Methodological Sheets by their relevance to the e-textile life cycle. Preliminary results from the worker group indicate that employment relationships, health and safety, sexual harassment, equal opportunities, and fair wages are high priorities, each selected by at least 70% of respondents. Furthermore, the framework identifies local employment and safe living conditions as vital for communities, while health, transparency, and end-of-life responsibilities are the primary concerns for consumers. Ultimately, this research establishes a foundational basis for data collection, ensuring that the social performance of emerging e-textiles is assessed through a targeted, stakeholder-driven lens.

Integrating Social Value into Circular Waste-to-Energy Strategies for Humanitarian Settings: A Life Cycle Sustainability Approach

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Abstract:

Humanitarian operations often face critical constraints in infrastructure, technical capacity, and resource availability, which results in unmanaged waste streams and poses risks to both the environment and local communities. In such contexts, waste management decisions have strong social implications, influencing community health, safety, livelihood opportunities, and levels of participation in crisis response. Within the Bio4HUMAN project, an integrated framework is applied to assess circular waste-to-energy strategies capable of delivering environmental benefits alongside socio-economic value in two humanitarian settings: South Sudan and the Democratic Republic of the Congo. In this study, a combined environmental and social Life Cycle Assessment (LCA–SLCA) is used to compare the environmental and socio-economic benefits in the two sites, evaluating environmental improvements as well as employment generation, community empowerment, and enhancements in social well-being.

Anaerobic digestion (AD) represents a robust solution for organic waste valorisation, producing locally available energy while supporting safer and cleaner living conditions [1, 2]. Four AD configurations were examined: (i) a modular micro-AD unit designed for lignocellulosic residues; (ii) a single-stage thermophilic digester suitable for mixed biowastes; (iii) a mesophilic micro-biogas system for varied organic fractions; and (iv) a domestic digester for food or animal waste operating under mesophilic or thermophilic conditions.

Findings indicate that domestic-scale digesters offer the most practical and socially beneficial option for decentralised humanitarian contexts, beyond achieving notable environmental improvements up to 90% reduction in key impact categories. The technology requires minimal technical training, enabling rapid adoption by local users. The system also supports the production of a digestate that can enhance soil fertility, contributing to food security initiatives. Socially, domestic AD fosters local capacity building, reduces exposure to open dumping and burning, and creates opportunities for income generation by energy production and digestate utilisation. These aspects are particularly relevant in humanitarian scenarios, where

strengthening agency, dignity, and community cohesion is as critical as reducing environmental burdens.

Overall, the study underscores the need to integrate social dimensions into sustainability assessments of waste management solutions. The proposed combined LCA-LCC-social approach provides a holistic perspective that supports the selection of circular Waste-to-Energy options enhancing social resilience and contribute to more equitable humanitarian interventions.

Acknowledgements

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Sustainability Assessments of Plastics

Analyzing the environmental impacts and circularity of biobased colloids and their composite plastic materials

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Abstract:

Biopolymers are polymers derived from cells in living organisms such as animals, trees, plants, fungi, and microorganisms. Structural polysaccharides such as cellulose and chitin, are among the most widely used biopolymers nowadays. Currently, there are biodegradable cellulose-based materials that embody the principles of the circular economy and benefit the environment. While the environmental benefits of natural biopolymers are undeniable (e.g., local availability, renewability, biodegradability, ease of processing) and have been extensively implemented in multiple products, carefully assessing their environmental impact beyond simple green claims remains challenging.

In this absence of comprehensive studies in the literature that use standardised environmental impact metrics to demonstrate the environmental sustainability of biopolymers, we aim to guide the laboratory-scale implementation of impact assessment. This is essential, as a first step in developing materials that can compete with fossil-based materials, which contribute to anthropogenic carbon emissions. In this regard, we utilized life cycle assessment (LCA) as an invaluable methodology for quantifying environmental impacts across multiple impact categories ensuring that potential trade-offs are not overlooked. Importantly, this information can be used to optimise materials, and reduce resource/water/energy consumption.

Our results reflect climate change potential values ranging from a minimum of 0.2 kg·CO₂-eq·kg^{ffl} for unbleached cellulosic pulp to 50.8 kg·CO₂-eq·kg^{ffl} for nanocelluloses obtained

through top-down isolation. Bottom-up approaches for biocolloids appear to render lower impact values. Beyond climate change potential and water consumption, our analysis also focuses on emerging impact metrics, such as criticality or material circularity. Actually, isolating biopolymers from biomass is a more circular process and requires lower amounts of critical materials than the fossil-derived materials used as a benchmark. These aspects are increasingly relevant towards an holistic understanding of the environmental impact, particularly when utilizing biobased colloids and their composite plastic materials, which can be utilized in high-tech applications such as optical sensing, counterfeiting, batteries, and environmental remediation, to replace critical raw materials. We also observed large variabilities in terms of climate change potential, acidification, freshwater ecotoxicity, marine eutrophication, human toxicity and water use in the manufacture of natural biopolymers. Thus, we identify scalability as one of the most significant challenges in advancing the commercial adoption of biobased composites.

Reusing Shredded Waste Cable Insulation in Geopolymer Slabs: Life Cycle Assessment, Composite End-of-Life Prediction, and Introduction of Longevity and Loop Factors

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Abstract:

Electrical cables at the end of their primary service life are recycled for their metallic components. However, the insulation, due to its complex composition and potential hazardous substances, is considered waste, which is landfilled or incinerated. Because rubber has analogous end-of-life pathways, the hypothesis is that waste insulation from electric cables has the potential to be reused as a secondary raw material in construction, at least as aggregates.

Therefore, shredded cable insulation was embedded into the geopolymer slurry on the exposed surface of the geopolymer slab in the maximum possible amount and left to cure at room conditions [1]. Without the cable insulation, geopolymer slabs exhibit high slipperiness and cannot be used, even in low-frequency areas, making electrical cable waste a vital ingredient for the composite product [1]. However, the end-of-life pathways for such composites remain unclear, because geopolymers (alternative “green” cements) are still largely bound to laboratory research. Nonetheless, in this study, several options were envisaged:

(i) reuse of coarsely crushed slabs to fill the wire mesh fence,

(ii) reuse of the intermediate fraction as aggregates in concrete, either with or without the top layer containing cable insulation,

(iii-a) reuse of the fine-milled composite without cable insulation (sieving) as a precursor for the 2nd level geopolymer with lower mechanical performance [2], where insulation can be reused again for the 1st level geopolymer or incinerated for energy or landfilled, and

(iii-b) reuse of fine-milled composite as a source of aluminium and silicon for cements, with and without cable insulation (sieving, followed by reuse, incineration, or landfill), to be calcined along with other cement ingredients. The presence of insulation material during calcination is considered to lower the need for energy.

While the data connected with the synthesis of the composite are primary or collected from the literature, data for waste cable insulation are from the Ecoinvent v3.11, and data for reuse are either from the literature or estimated. For the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), the LCIA method ReCiPe Midpoint (H) was used in the open-source software OpenLCA 2.5.

While keeping the material in use (delaying its end-of-life) decreases the environmental impact, it also makes the same material unavailable for other purposes, which consequently must rely on primary raw materials. To determine when the material will re-enter the system, the longevity and loop factors were introduced and applied to the geopolymer composite with embedded shredded cable insulation.

Closing the plastic packaging loop: Assessing the Environmental Impact of Circular Economy Innovations in DRS and RVM

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Abstract:

Plastic packaging remains one of the most pressing sustainability challenges of our time, largely due to its persistent presence in ecosystems and its environmental footprint when not managed properly. Conventional practices often lead to substantial waste, resource depletion and increased greenhouse gas emissions. To address this issue, innovative tools such as Deposit Return Systems (DRS) and Reverse Vending Machines (RVMs) are gaining attention by increasing collection rates and recycling efficiency, as well as promoting circularity. By reducing plastic pollution in the environment and improving the quality of secondary raw materials, these systems enable reuse and significantly less reliance on virgin plastics.

This study explores, through a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), the environmental benefits of integrating DRS and RVMs, providing insights into their role in sustainable waste management. The results demonstrate that integrating these solutions into national and corporate strategies is not only effective in mitigating environmental impacts, but is also essential for aligning with global sustainability goals and circular economy objectives.

This study has been conducted in collaboration with the Reconomy's innovation hub, CircuLab. Reconomy is a leading UK group specializing in sustainable resource management, recycling and circular economy solutions, operating globally in over 80 countries, supporting businesses with green technologies and resource-saving strategies designed to close the circularity gap. By applying the latest concepts in sustainability science and resource management, CircuLab develops impactful circular economy solutions that reduce waste and emissions, while increasing resource recovery.

A comparative life cycle assessment of fossil fuel-based plastic and nature-based single-use wet wipes

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Abstract:

The use of single-use wet wipes has increased since the COVID-19 pandemic as personal hygiene gained heightened emphasis, leading to a concurrent expansion of the global wet wipe market. This rise in consumption has led to an increase of single-use wet wipe waste, thereby amplifying the associated environmental burden. Fossil fuel-based plastic wet wipes, in particular, contribute to micro- and nanoplastic pollution and pose significant waste management challenges. These impacts highlight the need for regulatory intervention. The European Union(EU) enacted the Single-Use Plastics Directive (SUPD) to regulate certain items, including wet wipes. In South Korea, more than 90% of foodservice restaurants use single-use wet wipes, and cafés are likewise recognized as major points of consumption. Most single-use wet wipes are produced using polyester–rayon blended fabrics, although nature-based pulp wet wipes have recently been introduced. This study evaluates the potential environmental impacts of fossil fuel-based and nature–based single-use wet wipes. A life cycle assessment(LCA) was conducted using openLCA 2.5 and the Ecoinvent 3.11 database, covering manufacturing, transportation, and end-of-life (Cradle-to-Grave) processes. The functional unit was defined as 1 ton of single-use wet wipes. The climate change impact of 1 ton of the rayon 50% and polyester 50% wet wipes resulted in 5.31 ton CO₂-eq for the entire life cycle. The impact category of energy resources (non-renewable fossil) was estimated at around 1.74 ton oil-eq, which is attributed to fossil fuel consumption during the production and manufacturing of fossil fuel-based plastics. This study quantitatively compared the environmental impacts of the two product types. It provides foundational evidence to support policies aimed at reducing the consumption of plastic-based wet wipes, promoting a transition to natural alternatives, and establishing future management strategies of single-use plastic.

Toward circular plastics: Life-cycle-guided design PLA nanocomposites reinforced with bio-derived nano-fibrils and montmorillonite

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Abstract:

Polylactic acid (PLA) and its nanocomposites reinforced with nano-fibrillated cellulose (NFC) and sodium montmorillonite (NaMMT) or organically modified montmorillonite (Cloisite 30B) were produced using solution casting and electrospinning techniques. The study aimed not only to assess how cellulosic nano-fibrillar reinforcements (CNFR), in combination with layered silicates, influence the structural and thermal properties of PLA, but also to evaluate the sustainability advantages of electrospinning as a low-energy, low-waste fabrication method and to explore how the resulting materials contribute to circularity in biopolymer systems. Morphological and thermal behaviors were evaluated using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), and X-ray Diffraction (XRD).

Electrospinning yielded well-aligned nanofibrous structures, enhancing morphological uniformity while offering a comparatively sustainable processing route due to its low-temperature operation, compatibility with greener solvents, and minimized material waste. A Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) was conducted to evaluate the environmental implications of producing PLA-based nanocomposites. The reliance on renewable feedstocks such as PLA and NFC supports reduced carbon footprints and aligns with sustainability and circular-economy strategies. The combination of bio-based polymers, recyclable reinforcements, and efficient processing demonstrates a viable pathway toward more sustainable plastics systems.

This work highlights the potential of repurposable, reusable, and recyclable bio-derived materials as alternatives to conventional petroleum-based plastics. By improving performance through nanostructuring and adopting greener fabrication methods, the study contributes to future plastics strategies focused on reducing consumption, refusing unnecessary products, advancing recycling technologies, and promoting high-value repurposing. The findings illustrate how next-generation biopolymer nanocomposites can form the foundation of circular, low-impact material systems that support global efforts toward sustainable plastic futures.